

ZURO

1974

*The Magazine of the History Society
Umtali Boys' High School*

ZURO 1974

No. 7

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EDITORIAL.

A businessman, before entering into a new enterprise, will first look back into the past to discover the fate of similar such commitments before him. He will want to find out as much as he can before taking the final step. And what is life but a series of new enterprises? Everybody wants to be aware of the possibilities the future holds before advancing forward.

There is no way of planning for the future but by investigating the past; history is our only guide. To take a practical example - someone arriving late at the cinema finds it difficult to understand what he sees on the screen because he does not know what preceded it. Nor can he anticipate the way in which the film might develop. Life is the art of learning from other people's mistakes and the surest way of doing this is to read articles, histories and autobiographies pertaining to relevant situations in the past.

'Zuro', in printing articles of historical relevance, is not only providing a body of dialectic experience but is also, we hope, satisfying the curiosity and desire for knowledge that is common to every man. "What is all knowledge," asked Thomas Carlyle, "but recorded experience and a product of past history?"

History is life, and therefore the basis of all subjects. Without a background of history economics is mere mathematics, architecture little more than engineering, travel nothing but a more or less uncomfortable means of locomotion. History puts interest into life; 'Zuro' adds interest to history.

I.Gwyther.

CHAIRWOMAN'S REPORT.

Philippa Wyrley-Birch.

1974 has been a good year for the History Society both in terms of attendance at meetings and active participation in the Society's activities. The enthusiasm amongst members, particularly those from the lower ranks of the school, has been encouraging and is a healthy sign for the future.

A request came forward for a variation in the topics of meetings and consequently a wide range of speakers addressed the Society covering a considerable variety of subjects. Mr. D.Meikle commented on current affairs, Mr.Morley spoke on the Hellenic Civilisation, Mr.Chadder contrasted those conditions faced by school leavers in 1934 with those of today, Dr. MacKenzie from the University of Rhodesia spoke on Roman Britain and Mrs MacLean twice came to speak about her forthcoming book, "The Guardians." Mr.Barnes and several members of the Society gave an illustrated account of their trip to Great Zimbabwe, explaining many aspects of the ruins. Several members, before making a trip to Salisbury to address the Prehistory Society of Rhodesia, presented their topic to this Society, namely the battle of Mhanda Hill.

The highlight of the outdoor activities was a five day trip to Zimbabwe where members were able to examine the usual attractions of Zimbabwe as well as do some work for the Curator - a survey of the South East Ruins. A day excursion was made to Inyanga during the August holidays where Mr. Storry is excavating an unusual lone pit structure in the Pungwe District, and a similar excursion was made to Devuli Ranch at the invitation of R.Bridges of Upper Sixth to examine some Zimbabwe-type ruins. Afternoon trips were organised to St. Augustine's Mission and around the old buildings of Umtali.

In March the film, "Hitler - The Last Ten Days" was shown and was very well attended, with the welcome addition of girls from Marymount.

It is pleasing to note that both the 1972 and 1973 copies of 'Zuro' received favourable reviews in the "Rhodesiana" magazine. We are also pleased to have had letters from as far afield as America, Canada, England and Israel requesting copies of 'Zuro'. This is most encouraging and suggests that the Society is not afflicted by the apathy that seems to prevail in so many societies.

I would like to convey, on behalf of the Society and particularly of the Committee, our thanks to Mr.Barnes, our President, for the time devoted to and work done for the benefit of the Society. As Chairlady I extend my grateful thanks to Mr.Barnes for his unending encouragement, to Mike Morkel for his thankless work as a most efficient secretary, to Ralph Allen for his money-grabbing job as treasurer, to Iain Gwyther for his work with 'Zuro', to Robert Plowes who has combined the work of Archivist and Research Co-ordinator most effectively, and finally to all on the committee for putting up with the female element in the chair!

I hope that the enthusiasm of the members will not wane and that active participation will increase, for in that way the Society becomes more beneficial to all concerned. I would like to take this opportunity, on behalf of all those who are leaving, to wish the Society every success with its activities in 1975. Those who are returning I wish every success for the future.

TREASURER'S REPORT.

R.Allen. 16.

<u>Credit</u>		<u>Debit.</u>	
Subscriptions	£ 25.00	Film costs	£ 25.00
Film - "Hitler."	60.25	Zimbabwe Excursion:	
Zimbabwe Excursion	93.34	Costs	93.34
Donations by Mr. Ford and Mrs Izzett.	6.00	Awards	11.00
Sales of Zuro 1973.	5.25	Committee Expenses	11.00
Estimated Income of Zuro 1974.	25.00	History Prize	4.20
		Estimated Expenditure Zuro 1974.	60.00
	<u>215.84</u>		<u>204.54</u>

Excess Income over Expenditure : £ 11.30.

It is pleasing to note that income exceeds expenditure, a result of the worthwhile fund-raising activities on the part of the Society.

We have, one again, over fifty paid-up members whilst many more have attended two or more meetings without paying their subs.

We are grateful to Karen Gibson for her help in maintaining the high UGHS membership, and to Mrs. P.Izzett and Mr.J.Ford for their generous donations to and keen interest in the Society.

MEMBERSHIP.UGHS.

T.Cloete	S.Turner	C.Duguid	K.Northern
S.Eland	C.van de Ruit.	A.Elias	A.Ogilvie
A.Fairbanks	P.Veitch	* I.Gwyther	A.Paton
K.Gibson	* P.Wyrley-Birch	* J.Harris	R.Picton
E.Grobler		A.Hill	* R.Plowes
G.Hapgood	<u>UBHS.</u>	A.Hinwood	S.Thomas
S.Hough	R.Allen	G.Holcroft	J.Tweedie
D.Hunt	N.Bailey	R.Jones	D.van de Ruit
E.Iamb	H.Ball	S.Kavalieratos	P.van de Westhuysen
D.Iatham	R.Bentley	P.Langlois	G.West
G.Manders	R.Buckley	M.Morkel	D.Warwick
S.Mason	* J.Carroll	P.Morkel	E.Willers
D.Stuart	* T.Carroll	* B.Nicholas	* D.Williams.
	R.de Zoeten	* P.Nicholas	* Zimbabwe Excursion.

NURSERY RHYMES

According to Dr. Edward Southern, an American physician, some nursery rhymes are merely ditties to frighten children into being good. But others are serious satirical commentaries on the times, many dating back to the 15th, and are definitely aimed at adults.

Scattered throughout Zuro are some of these rhymes, which have been taken from the "International History" Magazine, issues 14 and 21. For example:

Ring Around the Roses refers to the round, rosy-red inflammation of the lymph glands which characterised the infectious phase of the plague. A pocket full of posies was to reduce the stench of the discharging glands. "We all fall down" really means "We all fall dead!"

HISTORY SOCIETY COMMITTEE.

	<u>1974</u>	<u>1975.</u>
Chairman	P.Wyrley-Birch	M.Morkel
Hon. Secretary	M.Morkel	I.Gwyther
Hon. Treasurer	R.Allen	R.Allen
Committee Member and Editor of Zuro	I.Gwyther	S.Gilmour
Research Co-Ordinator and Archivist	R.Plowes	R.Plowes
UGHS Representative	K.Gibson	D.Hunt

Research Co-ordinator's Report.

R.Plowes.

The research work undertaken by the Society this year has differed from the work done in previous years in that we have concentrated our attentions on collecting oral tribal traditions and records rather than interviewing pioneer descendants.

A sub-committee consisting of P.Nicholas, T.Carroll and myself was formed in the first term and with Mr Barnes' assistance we set out to investigate oral traditions about the battle of Mhanda Hill. We interviewed people from the opposing sides, namely from the Manyika and Vaungwe tribes, and the project was written up and presented to the Prehistory Society of Rhodesia in the Queen Victoria Museum, Salisbury. Next year this topic could be continued and members of the Saungweme tribe could be interviewed as they played a crucial part in the battle.

My attendance at the Ranche House College School of Archaeology could provide the basis of future sub-committee research, linking oral traditions with archaeology. There is a wide scope for such work in Manicaland and so could be a worthwhile exercise.

Work in the school museum has progressed slowly as the large pile of early school photographs has been sorted and organised. Most of these photographs have required identification and mounting and there is still much work to be done. A selection of these photographs has been organised into a display and has been exhibited in the foyer of the school along with early letters to the school. I must thank Mr Barnes, T.Carroll and P.Nicholas for their help in preparing this display.

Some early Masonic regalia which belonged to Mr T.B.Hulley and was given to us by his son Mr C.M.Hulley, was returned to the Masonic Lodge in town. Next year the National Historical Association of Rhodesia is organising a display of pre-1920 material and it is likely that some material from our museum will be included in that display.

The museum has not been open to the public so far this year but we hope to have a photographic display on show on Gala day.

In Heywood's "Four P's", written in 1543, a Palmer, a Pardoner, a Poticary and a Pedlar disputed as to which one of them could tell the greatest lie. The Palmer said he had never seen a woman out of patience; whereupon the other three P's threw in the sponge saying that such a falsehood could not possibly be outdone!

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY : 8th FEBRUARY, 1974.

CURRENT AFFAIRS : SOME COMMENTS.

Mr. D.Meikle.

"We are as schoolchildren," wrote Albert Einstein. "We shall never understand the true nature of things." But it is only by a study of history that we can acquire some understanding of the world around us. For example, asked Mr Meikle, had anyone considered what life would be like today if the Second World War had not occurred? Winston Churchill, in the preface to his "History of the Second World War," called it the "unnecessary war," meaning that no war should have been so easy to avoid. In 1935 for example, when Mussolini invaded Abyssinia, Emperor Hailie Selassie pleaded his case before the League of Nations and made quite clear the mounting Fascist threat to the world. But the League, without an army, was powerless, and reluctant, to stem the totalitarian tide. It is up to the "new generation," by a study of history, to avoid making the same mistakes in the future.

"The world's political problems," said Mr Meikle, "are people's problems," and it is these basic individual problems, of which there are three, which are the main causes of war :

- (a) greed for power and for material goods;
- (b) racialism, whether called tribalism or nationalism ("every man is a racist and he who denies it is a liar;")
- (c) ideology, the two most pronounced being capitalism and communism.

Mr Meikle believes the United Nations to be the "original toothless bulldog" but at least the powers are prepared to get together even if their record on major issues is unimpressive.

The European Common Market.

Potentially the greatest economic, political and military power in the world but, because of racialism, it lacks cohesion. This can be seen in the present oil crisis in which France has negotiated directly with the oil-producing countries, content to leave Holland completely deprived of oil.

The Middle East.

The real loser in the Middle East has been the United States because she backed Israel beyond the grounds of reason: America must defend Israel but not the captured lands. By supporting Israel's aggression America has lost her supply of cheap oil, as has the world. The only good thing America did was to stop Israel destroying Egypt and Syria: if the Israeli advance had continued the war would in all probability have escalated beyond control. As it was Russia gained by helping the injured party.

Whilst Israel continues to hold the captured lands the position remains explosive. (The exception is the Golan Heights, which Israel needs to secure her north-eastern border in the light of past Syrian aggression.) Any peace treaty must acknowledge -

- (a) the boundaries of Israel;
- (b) Israel's right to exist.

In this respect Kissinger's feat of achieving peace and getting both sides to maintain that peace will probably be recognised as one of the greatest diplomatic achievements of any one man.

The Oil Crisis.

A Californian Professor of Geology has calculated that

- 90% of the world's oil remains undiscovered;
- known oil reserves will last for 100 years.

The United States is the world's largest single producer of oil, but by 1980 the development of substitutes for oil should encourage :

- (a) more electric cars;
- (b) more public transport.

The real threat however lies in the increased price of oil: escalating inflation will be accompanied by a serious monetary imbalance. As the Arabs money reserves increase (it has been estimated that by the end of 1975 the Arabs will hold one third of the world's monetary reserves) so will they spend more money on sophisticated arms - surely a potential for evil. Abu Dabi for example earns \$30 000 for every one of the 80 000 men, women and children in the state. Already it has placed orders for Mirage IV aircraft.

Rhodesia.

For the African the most tragic aspect of recent history is the "crisis of expectation." He has been led to believe that it is only the lack of opportunity and of education which has prevented him from taking over. He now has the education and therefore awaits only the opportunity.

The whites have two basic Anglo-Saxon qualities - a sense of fair play and a sense of tolerance. The African however, who is more race-conscious than the white, regards the European as an outsider, as someone who can always go home.

Bishop Muzorewa told Mr Meikle that the African is more politically conscious than is the European. This is explainable in terms of his background - his discussions around the indaba tree - but could it be the white man's undoing? The present government is trying to appease African demands for power by granting the African powers of local government in the T.T.L.'s and by granting him advisory powers in townships. This is not enough for either the African or the rest of the world, and yet multi-racialism is undesirable: the whites would be swamped, an exodus would result and another "banana republic" would come into existence. Whatever course is chosen someone is going to be hurt.

Bishop Muzorewa has suggested that multi-racial schools and hospitals are our only hope, but that would mean a black/white ratio of 22:1 in the classroom or in the ward. European standards of culture would undoubtedly be affected. An America for example the negro is holding back the education of the whites: the negro is more boisterous and matures more quickly with the result that there is much bullying and friction; hence the presence of armed policemen in the schools.

Terrorism.

The terrorists are attempting to scare the whites into political capitulation and until we have a black government we will have to live with terrorism - the terrorists are not interested in a settlement with Britain. Terrorism can be contained but a mass internal revolt could not be stopped; whilst we have a progressive and enlightened African policy such a revolt will not occur.

Mr Meikle was prepared to state publicly that he has every faith in this country and feels his children will be perfectly safe here.

World Agriculture.

A number of factors - floods, famine, the failure of the monsoons, the dispersal of the Peruvian current (hence inadequate plankton to feed the anchovies, the world's main source of plankton,) - have resulted in a rise in agricultural prices, especially of protein foods.

In 1972 America over-produced, hence the large exports. World demand has encouraged American farmers to plant heavily again and there is therefore a glut in the world (the E.C.M. destroys 900 tons of butter per month) to the detriment of the farmer - over-production means a serious reduction in prices.

Mr Meikle holds no sympathy for those countries which go hungry: it is due almost entirely, he claims to laziness. With the present "green revolution" (ie. hybrid wheat and rice) yields can be raised by as much as five or six times. In the Philippines Americans are planting five crops a year on the same piece of land: as the rice dries a quick crop is inter-planted, which in turn is inter-planted with a fodder crop, etc. In this way 72 people can be fed off one hectare. Holland, the most densely populated country in the world, feeds itself and still exports one third of its agricultural produce. In China, on each tam (about one tenth of an acre) a peasant lives, keeps his animals and grows his rice.

The Population Explosion.

Rhodesia's most pressing problem especially as Africans regard

- children as a source of wealth;
- birth control as a whiteman's trick to gain numerical superiority.

Even at the moment the T.T.L.s cannot produce sufficient food to feed the African population.

The more sophisticated countries have stabilised their population but the unsophisticated states, due primarily to an improvement in medicine and thus a decline in infant mortality, are experiencing a rapid population growth. The result is a serious imbalance between the sophisticated and unsophisticated, with the former unable to exert its control.

Mr Meikle concluded by reminding his audience that although we appear to get a preponderance of bad news, good news or happiness is often considered not newsworthy and therefore goes undetected.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 22nd FEBRUARY, 1974.

A THUMBSKETCH OF THE HELLENIC CIVILISATION Mr D.S.Morley.

Professor Toynbee, explained Mr Morley, has divided western civilisation into a number of periods, each of which ultimately collapsed because the incumbents were unable to solve their most pressing problems.

The two civilisations on which Mr Morley showed slides were :

1. The Aegean (or Cretean) Civilisation.
2. The Hellenic (Greek and Roman) Civilisation. This Professor Toynbee explained in terms of his 'Challenge and Response' theory - this civilisation represented the successful response to a number of challenges. Equally the civilisation declined when it failed to respond successfully to internal and external challenges. What challenges finally toppled the Hellenic Civilisation?

- (i) the threat of anarchy as people flocked to the towns.
- (ii) the over-population of cities, which was partly solved by colonisation until this was halted by the development of the Carthaginian Empire.

Threats of external attack (particularly during the Archaic Period, 700-500 BC and from the Persians) were solved by fortified towns and by the unification of Sparta and Athens.

- (iii) The failure to maintain unity within the empire. The Hellenic culture, spread to Asia Minor by men such as Philip of Macedonia and Alexander the Great, resulted in the growth of super-powers such as Rome, Carthage and Macedonia. However it was the Romans who proved to be triumphant and imposed peace by force (300-31BC). The golden era of Rome was from 31BC-235AD and coincided with the spread of Christianity. In the fifth century the west collapsed however under the weight of the Barbarian invasions. Nevertheless it was the rejuvenation of this civilisation one thousand years later which laid the basis of our society and culture today.

Mr Morley illustrated his talk with some superb slides which showed the Aegean and Hellenic civilisations in their many different aspects.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 8th MARCH, 1974.

1934 - 1974 : A CONTRAST.

Mr. W.J.Chadder.

The difficulty in history, said Mr Chadder, lies in its recording. Before 1900 for example, all historical records tended to be orthodox; after 1900 there are so many different records, each presenting its own interpretation of history, that it is left to the individual to strike a balance and to determine for himself what is meaningful.

In 1934 the British Empire was very much a world force but there were clouds on the school leaver's horizon, particularly the increasing threats posed by Germany, Italy and Japan. Germany, fully recovered from the First World War, was riding the wave of the megalomaniac Adolf Hitler. As a racialist and dictator with total power, Hitler was introducing his programme to effectively curtail the freedom of the individual, surely the basis of all libertarian ideology. Mussolini was a pale shadow of Hitler but no less effective for all that; in the east Japan was fast becoming a power to be reckoned with.

The dictators excelled in the art of "brinkmanship" - that is, using the threat of war to gain one's demands although always avoiding a final confrontation. Nowhere is this better seen than in Hitler's foreign policy after 1934, but it is evident too in the "Sawdust Caesar's" occupation of Abyssinia - the League of Nations was fully revealed in all its hapless glory. The Spanish Civil War was another threatening cloud on the horizon, with Russia supporting the extreme left and the Axis powers supporting the extreme right. Franco's victory (right wing) was another blow for western civilisation; for Germany and Italy it served as a full dress rehearsal for the Second World War. It was the unabashed turn to authoritarianism that was to make this conflict inevitable.

The war was postponed for a year by the actions of Chamberlain in meeting Hitler three times in September, 1938. Europe existed on a thread of futile hope and preparations for war continued unchecked. Unlike the First World War it was to be a war of ideology - democracy versus dictatorship - with Russia in the initial instances an uncertain quantity.

Today's problems are similar, only the characters have changed. The democratic world still clings to its libertarian ideals with its associated values of individual freedom. On the opposing side is the communist bloc which consists of no less than totalitarian dictatorships. And what is the real difference between the two? - it is the rule of law. The fact that in a democracy the executive is separated from the executive and the legislative; the fact that in a democracy the law is not only stable but public and is within easy reach of every individual.

There is however an additional threat today, and that is as is posed by the non-aligned nations. These nations can be divided into three sections - countries like India; the oil-producing states; the underdeveloped countries symbolised by the O.A.U. These non-aligned states can be compared to vultures, always grabbing and upsetting the balance.

One must find one's own solutions to the various problems faced by today's world. History however often provides avenues of relevant experience - we can move forward more successfully if we study history and thereby gain an insight into the solutions that people have devised to overcome problems that they have faced.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THIS HISTORY SOCIETY, 29th MARCH, 1974.

ROMAN BRITAIN.

Dr. J. MacKenzie.

The influence of the Romans is evident even today in almost every sphere of British life. But what brought the Romans to Britain in the first place? Partly the attraction of minerals, partly agricultural and partly the need to conquer the Britons who were making periodic incursions across the Channel.

Upon arrival the Romans established in Britain a replica of their life style and culture of Rome. This was particularly so in south England - the north was still relatively barbaric and was therefore more military in nature. Agricola in particular mounted a series of campaigns (78-85 AD) which gained for the Romans large areas of Scotland and Wales. To strengthen his conquests Agricola built great defensive systems, forts and signal stations, but he was eventually forced to retreat. This forced the realisation that a short frontier would be more easy to defend, hence a series of walls in the north.

The first was Hadrian's Wall, stretching from Tynne to the Solway, some seventy nine miles long with twenty forts, castles every mile and turrets every half mile. In front was a ditch, behind was a road for easy movement of troops. A second wall was built further north - Antonines Wall. Only thirty seven miles long, it was a matter of turf laid on top of a stone base. It was sixteen feet high and included the normal ditch and defence structures. It was manned by Legionaires (true Romans) and Auxilliaris but was permanently overrun in 180 AD - it had lasted for forty years. Hadrian's Wall was abandoned in 386 AD after it too was continually overrun.

Dr MacKenzie showed some very interesting slides of Roman relics in Britain, both exposed and in the process of excavation.

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY, 1st AUGUST, 1974.

"THE GUARDIANS"

Mrs J. MacLean.

Due to an unfortunate clash attendance at the meeting was small; Mrs MacLean consequently agreed to postpone her prepared talk and to discuss informally her forthcoming book.

What prompted Mrs MacLean to write a book on the Dept. of Native Affairs, the forerunner of the Dept. of Internal Affairs? Firstly she felt the need to draw attention to the devotion, courage and selfless service of the Native Commissioners and their essential contribution to the founding of this country; secondly as an inspiration to the future - a knowledge of history means both an appreciation of our heritage and confidence for the future - and the challenge we face is very similar to that faced by early Native Commissioners. The immediate cause was Mrs MacLean stumbling over the grave of Henry Herman Ruping virtually in her garden at Mrewa! Immediate enquiries revealed that almost nothing was known about him but after

research in the Archives this typically young Native Commissioner (22 years old) began to come alive. He had joined the B.S.A.Co., done some prospecting and, almost broke, joined the Native Affairs Dept. and been sent to Mtoko.

Being married to a former Native Commissioner meant that many events were brought to Mrs MacLean's attention. When her husband was stationed at Mrewa, for example, they lived in a large, typically Rhodesian house. One night, whilst in the bathroom, Mrs MacLean heard footsteps coming through the kitchen and living room to the verandah and yet investigation showed that there was no one there. Similarly she and her husband would both wake up simultaneously to find the bedroom door opening. This, Mrs MacLean is convinced, was the ghost of Wiri Edwards, the Native Commissioner who had built the house in 1901.

Edwards had been sent to Mrewa in 1893, the reply to his request for instructions being, "You have a bible and a compass - off you go!" The senior Native Commissioner, Mr Erabant, expected him to build his hut, establish his boundaries by consultation with surrounding Native Commissioners, make a map of the area and contact the locals, the latter proving very timid. To overcome this timidity the Native Commissioner would send out messengers, variously attired in skins and feathers and carrying an assegai, to tell the Africans that the Commissioner had come to help. Then, sitting in the dust, the Commissioner would meet the locals and explain to them the necessities of government, law and order and tax collection. In this way there developed a very genuine friendship and affection between the races that characterised the dealings of all the early members of the Native Department.

Why was tax collection so important? Firstly to gain respect - the Mashona would pay tribute to the European government in exactly the same way that they had paid tribute to Lobengula. Secondly it was a valuable lesson in contributing to the economy, and because they had contributed the Africans felt they had a stake in the new developments taking place. The tax patrols themselves were regarded by the Africans as the social event of the year and provided the Native Commissioner with the means of hearing all the prevailing problems of the people of the district.

.....

The book took eight years to research, this being done in the Archives, by writing letters to surviving Native Commissioners and by personal contact - talking to Native Commissioners and recording the conversation on tape. This was not as easy as it sounds - Mr Orpen's Irish brogue was so broad that the tape had to be played back six times before a meaningful transcription could be made!

This information was then transferred to post cards and filed alphabetically either biographically or under subject headings. The final written account was completed by Mrs MacLean in her spare time whilst at Melsetter, and was done chronologically, which had its difficulties in that so many different persons kept reappearing throughout the text that it was not easy to keep track of them all and so make it meaningful.

The book was accepted by the first publisher to whom it was offered who explained that, as it would cost some \$16000 to produce, he would have to establish his sales first, much of which would be outside Rhodesia. As this was shortly after UDI there were exchange control difficulties, hence the delay in production.

In a pre-publication newsletter the editor of the "Books of Rhodesia" series had this to say about "The Guardians" -

"... an absorbing history of the S.R. Native Affairs Dept., its employees and their families. The Department, backbone of the administration in the early and middle years, was charged with the herculean task of reconciling, as painlessly as possible, two very different racial cultures. That it managed to do this so successfully is a tribute to those dedicated officials, and their wives, who spent the best years of their lives in government service in the remote areas of Rhodesia. Through narrative, anecdote and perceptive comment, Joy MacLean illuminates their trials, joys and accomplishments and, in doing so, expresses that tribute in the clearest terms."

A VISIT TO ST.AUGUSTINE'S MISSION.

In June a party from the History Society was invited to St. Augustine's Mission by Father Prosser and the Sixth Form students of the school.

The early mission farm had been established by Bishop Knight-Bruce in 1891 after he had brought up from Beira the three nursing sisters, Rose Blennerhasset, Lucy Sleeman and P. Welby. The site was determined by a nearby waterfall which was to be used to work a mill - the waterfall is still functional.

The Bishop was greatly helped by John Wilkins, a coloured who claimed to have been with David Livingstone. Wilkins died in February, 1892, and his grave can be seen in the mission cemetery.

Our party was shown round by the African students; we were shown the beautiful church, the dormitories, classrooms and kitchens and the most attractive library. The school, which was the first African secondary school in the country, is co-educational and teaches up to 'A' Level. All the secondary pupils are boarders and such is the reputation of the school that they come from all over the country to attend. Punishment includes manual labour but the most severe treatment is for pupils to be kept away from the school for three days! In the primary section some of the pupils walk from as far away as Christmas Pass to attend.

After tea we divided into two. The more junior of the group listened as Father Prosser, Principal of the school, explained the history and function of the school. The seniors were invited to hear an African Sixth Form History student present a paper on 'Imperialism.' The standard of the paper was most impressive and the agitated discussion which followed had to be prematurely ended as the time approached for us to leave.

All in all a most interesting and informative afternoon; we feel that it is the kind of experience that all Rhodesian school children should be encouraged to undertake.

The expression "Son of a Gun" originated when all members of a family went with the English sailors on board the 'Men of War' frigates.

During long voyages due to limited space on board, many births took place "under the guns."

MINUTES OF A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY : 19th SEPTEMBER.

SOME INCIDENTS IN THE 1896 REBELLIONS.

Mrs. J. MacLean.

There are different kinds of historians, Mrs MacLean noted, including the academic, who studies the subject intellectually but tends to gain for it its reputation of being 'dry as dust', and the scientific, who studies through a microscope the 'gyrations of the human being.' But history is life, and therefore both vital and eternal. It is also relevant in that we are an integral part of, and the result of, the past, and without a knowledge of that past we cannot adequately anticipate or mould the future. One of the purposes of Mrs Maclean's book, "The Guradians", is to combat ignorance about the past and thereby to provide, through the appreciation of the qualities of those who went before, an inspiration for the future.

In the early 1890's the BSACo. appointed a number of 'Field Cornets' to administrate the outlying areas of Rhodesia and to maintain law and order. In 1894 their title was changed to 'Native Commissioner', one of whom was H.H.Ruping, as described in Mrs Maclean's first talk to the Society. He was sent to collect tax from Mahonba's kraal but as he approached the rocky outcrop on which the kraal was situated he heard sounds to suggest drunken revelry. He camped at the bottom of the kopje, determined to collect taxes the next morning, but was soon approached by a shouting, aggressive horde who threatened to kill him. Walking through a hail of stones he stared directly at the ring leaders, stopped their onrush and sent them back to their kraal. He had no way of knowing that this aggressiveness was associated with the general outbreak of rebellion throughout the country.

Next morning Mahonda's people were still aggressive and so Ruping sent a runner to Salisbury. Gradually realising the widespread nature of the uprising he decided to warn the nearby farmers and prospectors. His camp was surrounded but he rode through and by evening had reached Mrewa. He lit a fire to make tea when a strange African appeared, claiming that all the Europeans in the area had been killed and offering to lead Ruping to the safety of his kraal. The young Native Commissioner was immediately suspicious and refused, deciding instead to ride throughout the night towards Salisbury.

By dawn he had reached the Shashi River and again stopped to light a fire when Mungati, an ex-messenger from Mtoko, appeared. He had, he claimed, been following Ruping all night and asked him to return to Mtoko for safety. Ruping agreed but as he turned to hand the reins of his horse to his messenger Mungati fired, shattering Ruping's elbow. Other natives appeared wielding assegais and Martini-Henrys but when Ruping retaliated they fled accompanied by his horse and his messengers. Ruping was left only with his greyhound dog and one messenger too badly wounded in the thigh to move. Leaving a trail of blood Ruping walked to the river to wash after which he lay down under a tree.

Mungati meanwhile had gone off to Diza's kraal and, with reinforcements, decided to beat both sides of the river. They came across Ruping asleep but he awoke when his dog barked and went to a rocky prominence in the river. The natives fired, killing Ruping and his dog as well as some of their fellows. Ruping's body was stripped and his bones together with those of his dog were discovered by Wiri Edwards about one year later.

Another incident concerns Archer Russell Ross who, as Native Commissioner of Rusape in 1896, was resented by Chief Makoni as a rival "white chief". Various reports made Ross realise that Makoni intended to kill all the Europeans and the African messengers in the area, and he therefore decided to ride to the kraal, first informing his messengers that if he had not returned by night-fall they were to bring all the Europeans into laager at Headlands.

As he arrived at the kraal the Waungwe rushed out with assegais but Ross calmly tethered his horse and demanded to see Makoni. He warned the chief not to get involved but could make no impression and therefore decided to leave, although as he walked out he was convinced his end had come. Makoni however had not given the order to attack and Ross thus escaped unscathed, riding all day to warn the nearby farmers and prospectors of the uprising. When 4 000 Waungwe did go on the rampage the following night they found the Europeans safely esconced in laager at Headlands.

Thomas Benjamin Hulley, nicknamed 'Tambudza' (the worrier) and Native Commissioner of Untali, detected unrest and decided to send his wife and two sons, Cecil and Frank, to Salisbury. Their carriage was threatened all the way but, unlike the next wagon to take that road, they arrived safely. Hulley did not know until the end of the rebellion that his family was safe.

Meanwhile he formed a well-organised laager at (Old) Untali but realising that the Manyika were gathering nearby he decided one night to ride out to talk to Mutasa. The natives, astonished at his fearlessness, allowed him right up to Mutasa's hut where he sat down and drank beer with the chief. Mutasa claimed that he was being pressurised by the Ndebele but Hulley persuaded him that the Europeans, with the help of the 'Great White Queen', were stronger and would protect Mutasa from his oppressors should he promise not to join the rebellion. Mutasa kept his promise. Hulley did not tell anyone of his journey and for many years it remained a secret.

William Longden (nicknamed 'Red Buffalo' because of his ginger beard) was sent by Rhodes to Gaza to persuade Gungunyana to remain loyal to the British in the face of Portuguese and German persuasion. There he remained for eight months, often under very difficult conditions.

When he was Native Commissioner at Tuli a European was run over by a wagon and had to have a leg amputated. There being no doctor it fell to Longden to perform the operation. Two policemen who were holding candles over the table fainted at the vital stage! but the patient survived - and his only anasthetic was a bottle of whiskey.

Longden moved to Melsetter as Native Commissioner and was called upon to entertain Rhodes, who was shocked at the shabbiness of the accomodation. Longden went on leave soon after and whilst in America met and married Mary Doone under rather fascinating circumstances. On his return to Melsetter he built for her 'The Gwasha', the American character of which is unmistakeable. It still stands and is said to be haunted by Longden's ghost.

William Driver, Native Commissioner in Gwelo, was called upon to distribute cattle to improve the quality of the native stock. In the act of distribution he heard of the outbreak of rinderpest and promptly had to destroy those cattle he had just handed out. This as well led to much misunderstanding and aggressiveness, and a tight situation from which he barely managed to escape.

The stories of these Commissioners should, Mrs Maclean argued, act as an inspiration to Rhodesian youth. The pioneers were no different to us; they experienced the same emotions of hope, frustration, boredom, courage and adventure. When one realises this one can counteract the pessimistic predictions sometimes offered of this country's future. After all the future rests in our hands, and our hands alone.

A VISIT TO PARLIAMENT.

H.Ball, 3A1.

At six o'clock on a cold Wednesday morning, 29th May, sixty ardent historians clambered aboard the bus in front of Crawford/Palmer dining room. Our purpose was to visit the Parliamentary exhibition celebrating fifty years of responsible government in Rhodesia. Unfortunately the bus proved to be extremely slow, taking $5\frac{1}{2}$ hours to reach Salisbury.

The exhibition was well organised and, together with several other groups of school children, we were kept on the correct route by green arrows. Unfortunately, despite all the officials standing by, nothing was explained to us verbally - there were explanatory plaques beneath each exhibit but we were not able to ask questions.

The first item was a portrait gallery of all past Prime Ministers and Governors of Rhodesia. In the House of Assembly we saw the elaborately carved Speaker's Chair, the Secretaries' Table where everything said in Parliament is recorded and the benches on either side of the House. In most democratic countries the party in power sits on the right of the speaker and the opposition on the left, but in Rhodesia the RF, having considerably more seats than the other parties, takes up both sides of the Assembly leaving the opposition to fill the cross benches at the end. On the table of the House the despatch boxes and oath books were on display.

The next exhibit was the progress of Rhodesia as depicted in stamps. This extensive display covered all major events from 1890 to the present day. There were also pictures of past Legislative Assemblies and Senates showing the development of parliament. There was a general exhibition showing the coat of arms, flags - old and new - and charts to show how parliament is run and laws passed. It included a series of cartoons satirising past events including U.D.I.

We saw busts of famous people, Rhodes, Selous and Smuts being among them. Here the ceremonial dress worn by the Speaker of the House was displayed, as were the ornate brass maces, one of which had come from the Assembly. When parliament is in session the mace is raised onto two clasps at one end of the Table of the House. When the Speaker leaves the chamber and parliament is officially no longer in session, the mace is taken down and placed on two clasps below the Table.

Finally we saw the Senate. Here everything is translated into three languages - English, Sindebele and Shona. The members of the Senate are not elected but are chosen by virtue of position. Thus a chief who cannot speak a word of English could well be a valuable member of the Senate.

We had lunch in the park and in the afternoon visited the Queen Victoria Museum which, despite the size of Salisbury, is not the National Museum. Particularly interesting was "The History of Man in Southern Africa", a display ranging from Prehistoric man through Bushman, Hottentot and Bantu to the pioneers and early settlers. The Museum also showed the evolution of life designed to a one year scale - it is amazing to see how much more happened in the last few days of December than in all the other months put together.

We finally left Salisbury at 3.30 pm, completing the return trip in $5\frac{3}{4}$ hours. We arrived home tired but satisfied after an interesting and informative day.

During the August holidays, with the aid of a school bursary, I was fortunate enough to attend the two week school of archaeology run by Ranche House College at Zimbabwe. The course was directed by Dr. Thomas Huffman and was directed at the amateur, giving him a knowledge of archaeological techniques as well as a background to Rhodesia's Stone and Iron Ages.

Our group of twenty people stayed in National Park chalets at Zimbabwe, the catering being done by staff of the College. We were kept fully occupied digging at a village site in the morning and attending lectures in the afternoons and evenings. The site at which we dug was a continuation of a previously excavated site alongside the museum at Zimbabwe. Basically the dig was divided into three metre squares and we excavated down to the daga walls and hut floors, collecting all pottery sherds and bones for later examination. Records were kept of each trench and the locations of important structures were noted and photographed. During the course of the dig some iron arrowheads were discovered along with beads and decorated pottery, especially in the area of the midden heap.

The lectures were delivered by Dr. Huffman and visiting lecturers, many accompanied by films and practical demonstrations. Dr. Huffman talked on the Early and Late Iron Age, discussing the traditions and phases and then on the ceramics associated with these cultures. He also dealt with methods of classifying, drawing and describing pottery finds and this was followed by a series of practicals in which we participated.

Mr. C.Cooke covered the Stone Age cultures with an emphasis on implement types and rock art. He illustrated his lectures with slides and we went on an outing to the nearby Chamavara Cave where there is an impressive frieze of rock art. Brother Kurt gave us a slide show dealing specifically with Rhodesian rock paintings.

One afternoon Mr.Raath and Dr.Sheppard travelled down from Salisbury to deliver lectures on faunal analysis and radio-carbon dating. Both of these topics are of importance to the archaeologist. Mr.Raath's lecture covered bone preservation and handling and the identification of more common bones as found by archaeologists. After the talk we attempted to reconstruct whole skeletons brought by Mr.Raath. Dr.Sheppard dealt with the principles and techniques of radio-carbon dating and the handling of samples for submission. He also spoke on the value of the dates and how to interpret them.

Professor van der Merwe flew up from Cape Town for a week and lectured on metallurgy and its use to the archaeologist. He also pointed out how copper and iron were used by the Iron Age peoples. The important topic of surveying was covered by Mr.Munro, the curator of Zimbabwe. The methods of mapping and surveying were mentioned to us and the next morning we mapped the site of our excavation using a plane table.

The technique of writing a scientific paper was described by Dr. Huffman as one is required to write a report on all excavations. Rather unexpectedly we were told to write a report on the dig on the final Saturday, the only day that it rained.

We went as well on a day's outing into the Chibi T.T.L. on the Beit Bridge Road. First we went to Chamakangwadza, a grantie kopje, where we made a surface collection of pot sherds and figurines. At a cave just below this hill we examined rock paintings and a piece of rare Bambata ware was found. After stopping at the Lundi River for lunch we visited a Zimbabwe-style ruin and then the Khami-style Lundi ruin.

During the school we were taken on a guided tour of the ruins and were given the latest scientific evidence of some of the features. Although nothing new emerged from this discussion, it served as confirmation that the builders of the ruins were of Bantu origin. With some people still favouring Arabic origins we had many interesting discussions. However the theory of Bantu builders who had trade links with the East coast Arabs is still the idea which I accept.

By attending this school one is qualified to conduct an excavation of limited size in Rhodesia. However one must obtain prior permission from the National Museums and Historical Monuments Commission as well as the consent of the land owner. There are also requirements on one's excavation permit with which one must comply. To gain a more competent knowledge of the subject it is advisable to attend at least two of these courses before directing a large dig.

I found the course a most worthwhile experience and would recommend it to people interested in archaeology, even if they have little intention of conducting large digs; it provides a fascinating basis for every interest in this field.

OLD BUILDINGS OF UMTALI.

On the afternoon of Monday, 30th September, twelve members of the Society visited some of Umtali's old buildings with Mr C.M.Hulley as our guide.

First stop was 'Utopia', the homestead of R.S.Fairbridge, the surveyor and father of Kingsley. When the walls were about four feet high the rains broke; thus Fairbridge put the doors and windows in place, erected poles with the roof on top and filled in the 'walls' with reed mats. Most of the iron sheeting for the roof had been carried up from Beira on the heads of natives.

The house 'Three Steps' (now 'Ventian' and owned by Mr Chadder) was built (literally) by Mrs Lily Fisher before 1900. She was living in the area when the township was still at Old Umtali, but when Rhodes bought the four farms Sable Valley, Waterfalls, Mountain View and Berkley that make up the present site of Umtali, Mrs Fisher was allowed to retain a plot on which to build, and in fact the materials for 'Three Steps' came up from Johannesburg.

Kopje House was the first hospital, the site being chosen because the high ground acted against the prevalent diseases malaria and blackwater fever. The first three doctors were Messrs Jackson, Craven and Howarth and the matron and six nurses were paid £600 per annum plus board and lodging and a return fare to Cape Town. The cost of hospitalisation was 4/9d. per day, and many of the old pioneers (Crawford, Palmer and Hulley) spent their last hours there.

The Club was completed in 1898, as were the Cecil Hotel, Government Offices, Residency and Stock Exchange. It was first designed as a hotel (Adams Hotel) but was not popular and in 1900 became the Umtali Club. It was famous for the lion's footprints in the bricks in the bar - the lion had chased a donkey through Engelbrecht's brick yard whilst the bricks were drying!

Finally we visited the 'Castle' which was begun by Colonel Methuen in 1913 and housed his collections of flags and arms. It was the Methuen brothers (Stuart and the Colonel) who erected the cross on Cross Kopje (1924.)

Unfortunately we did not have time to visit the first school, 52 Park Rd. Readers who would like to find out more about these buildings should refer to Mr. Hulley's article in the July 1971 edition of 'Rhodesiana', No.24.

GREAT ZIMBABWE.A DIARY OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY TRIP, 22nd - 26th APRIL.

The party of fifteen, together with Mr Barnes and Mr Harris, met outside the Staff Room on a cold, wet Monday morning. A little behind schedule we clambered into our modes of transport - the school's Thames Trader and Mr Barnes' car. The journey was slow but relatively uneventful as we stopped at Birchenough Bridge and again for lunch. In Fort Victoria we were delayed at the garage whilst minor repairs were completed on the truck. As we set off on the last stretch of our journey the fan belt on the truck broke and we had to return to the garage.

We arrived at the camping ground after sun-down, established camp and set about our first cooked meal. The result was pleasantly surprising; indeed we found the cooking to be of a consistently good standard throughout the camp.

That night we sat around the camp-fire talking and getting to know each other before getting to bed at 10 o'clock.

Tuesday.

A few eccentrics went up the Acropolis to watch the sun rise, followed by the rest of the party at a more reasonable hour.

The first scheduled visit of our itinerary was to the site museum and reconstructed Karanga Village. We spent an interesting hour gathering background information, especially as a safari tour arrived in the museum shortly behind us. We heard the guide outline her theory as to the origins of Zimbabwe; with her glib refusal to acknowledge the evidence immediately to hand we could understand how the myth of Zimbabwe is perpetuated.

At the Great Enclosure we wandered about taking photographs and eliciting information; it was getting late as we strolled through the Valley Ruins to the South East Ruins. Mr Munro, the Keeper, had given us the opportunity of surveying these ruins, a task we postponed until Thursday.

Back at camp the cooks and slaves prepared lunch whilst the remainder played with a rugby ball on the nearby golf course.

The Acropolis was the objective for the afternoon. We broke up into small groups to investigate the various enclosures and with the question "Who built Zimbabwe?" in mind and guide books in hand we attempted to understand the origins and functions of the various structures.

In the evening the ardent fishermen went to join Mr Harris at Lake Kyle (without tangible proof of success.) Supper was most welcome and after the inevitable cup of coffee some of the group settled down to a serious game of bridge with high stakes.

Wednesday.

The morning was one of free enterprise; it proved that if a schoolboy is not entertained he is quite happy to do nothing! Later in the morning some went swimming at the hotel whilst two of the more energetic hiked to the Kyle Dam Wall and surprisingly returned to fulfil their duties as cooks.

Lunch was early to enable everyone to tidy up before the trip to the Dutch Reformed Mission, Morgenster. Amid many groans full school uniform was donned and a loaded truck started along the road that leads to the mission. We were met by Rev. Heyns who guided us over this large station which is run by the Cape Province Dutch Reformed Church. It includes a school for the deaf, a printing house, a hospital, a church and, from the

western boundary, a magnificent view of the surrounding hills.

Thursday.

We were up early to prepare for a talk from the Keeper. Mr Munro laid before us the different theories concerning the Ruins before offering his own interpretation. Much of the 'mystery' of Zimbabwe was clarified by scientific evidence and common sense.

At the South-East Ruins we set up our plane table and began the survey which, with one break for lunch, was to take the whole day. The end result, reproduced on p.19, should prove valuable as it is the first time these particular ruins have been surveyed. We are proud to have received complimentary letters from Mr Munro and Mr Cooke, the latter of the Historical Monuments Commission.

Thursday night was spent around the camp fire and the party was introduced to the vagaries of "Matthew, Mark, Luke and John." The day finished on an hilarious note for some when a junior had the bright idea of dousing with cold water the sleeping form of one of the seniors!

Friday.

We broke camp and were soon on the road, arriving back in Umtali at 3.30 pm after an uneventful journey. It had proved to be a most enjoyable five days: socially stimulating and educationally beneficial.

We would like to thank all the parents who contributed to our camping equipment and to the kitchen; Rev. Heyns and Sister Ross; Mr Harris, who drove the truck under difficult circumstances; Philippa Wyrley-Birch who was i.c. catering, and all the cooks and slaves who contributed so willingly to the chores of camp life.

EARLY WHITE VISITORS TO ZIMBABWE.

B.Nicholas. 2A.

Rev. A.Merensky.

The first European to have heard about Zimbabwe in modern times appears to have been a German missionary, the Rev. A.Merensky. Like many other missionaries he took an interest in the historical tradition of the people amongst whom he worked.

It is not known if Merensky ever saw Zimbabwe but he had heard of it by 1862 and later in 1867 he told Karl Mauch, the German geologist, about it. Merensky, in a letter to a German magazine, said he had been told of the stone buildings by a Pedi chief, Sekukuni, who had visited the place many years earlier.

Adam Render.

Render is believed to have visited Zimbabwe in 1868 - the uncertainty is due to the fact that Render himself left no account of his adventures. He is presumed to have been an American hunter with a home in the Transvaal. His grave is thought to be near Zimbabwe although the site is unknown.

Karl Mauch.

Mauch was the man who made Zimbabwe known to the outside world. He was a geologist born in Germany in 1837 and it was he who made the first discovery of gold in Southern Africa at Bechuanaland in 1866. He later crossed the Limpopo with Henry Hartley and discovered the Tati Goldfield.

He heard of Zimbabwe from Merensky but did not actually visit the ruins until 1871. On his way to the ruins he was robbed of his trading goods; later he was found by a group of Karanga and taken to the Karanga

chief, Mapunsure. It was only a year later that Mauch was allowed to leave. He first sited the ruins from a hill which he was climbing, together with Render, to see a pot which the natives said moved by itself.

The Karanga were very suspicious of Mauch and tried to prevent him from visiting the ruins. As a result Mauch made his visit by night - presumably the Karanga were too scared to follow him. This and the dense bush, which successfully hid part of the ruins, must be kept in mind when considering the following description Mauch made of the ruins :

"Zimbabwe lies about 190 miles due west of Sofala. It consists of two principal monuments. The first is on top of a bare granite hill and the other is about half a mile south separated by a sandy valley.

"Considering first the hill ruin: the outer wall is a mass of rock three hundred feet long and sixty feet high, built with great daring on a curved cliff edge. It stretches in a straight line from east to west and for about 120 feet has a thickness of twelve feet at the bottom decreasing to six feet at the top and its height being about thirty feet. Inside this wall is a long quadrangular enclosure whose western boundary is bow shaped. In the collapsed part of this wall stone beams stand up perpendicularly for several feet at intervals of about eight feet. They appear to act as internal supports for the unmortared wall. I examined one of these beams on which a lot of carving had been done - it had an oval cross-section with axes of four and two-and-a-half inches and many ornamental designs engraved on its polished surface.

"The thinner inner walls have nearly all collapsed and so it is very difficult to make one's way over the heaps of rubble. From the inner enclosure towards the rocks on the summit of the hill run many covered passages probably in cracks and clefts, but maybe through great underground chambers. These passages however, obviously of early origin, have been blocked by kaffir walling.

"Further on I discovered an obscure little cave formed under a large overhanging boulder, in which lay a well proportioned, plain dish broken into two unequal pieces. The whole western slope of the hill was covered in debris which could mean this hillside was once terraced.

"The other ruin in the flat country about half a mile from the hill consists of a great circular wall about twenty four feet high, twelve feet thick at the base and eight feet at the top. Stone beams have also been used here to strengthen the walls as can be seen in several places where the upper part has collapsed.

"On the northern side is the entrance, originally only wide enough for one person and which is distinguished by a tree trunk resembling a cedar. Within run thinner walls curved to form a maze: the enclosures seem to have been used as refuge from pursuing natives as is shown by two circular places (often to be seen when some sheep and goats are kept together for the night.)

"On the upper part of the southern wall and within two feet of the top there are some layers of stone where one can see the remains of ornamental work (the Chevron pattern.)

"The most noticeable thing inside the circular building is a more or less conical tower thirty feet high. This lies opposite the entrance and near the southern part of the wall. Because of the debris piles up around its foot no entrance can be found. After

climbing up a creeper to its summit I found it to be eight feet in diameter and I then took up some stones but could find no hollow within. Two parallel walls which give access to the tower through a narrow entrance are decorated by double lines of black schist blocks of rounded form alternating with carefully trimmed granite block (the Rondeau pattern.)

"Adjoining the round building on the side facing the hill are many ruins of large buildings which do not conform to the tradition of mortared walling although the walls which can be seen tend to be rectangular in plan.

"Neither up on the hill nor down in the plain did I see any inscriptions which could have told me the builders of these puzzling structures. I had to appeal to the natives whose information took a long time to obtain. They took such an uncomfortable interest in my studies that one day I stopped all work and continued in private."

This description is interesting because Mauch tells of very few trees in the ruins and we know the ruins were full of trees in his day. Also Mauch describes Zimbabwe with much more rubble around than we know it today. In a perspective drawing of the Circular Building Mauch drew a ruin to the left of the building (looking from the Acropolis) which no longer exists.

Philips and Selous.

After Mauch's publications a number of hunters and travellers visited the ruins. The elephant hunter George Philips is believed to have been one of the earliest, arriving in 1872 to help Mauch prepare for his return journey. This visit is commemorated by the name "Philips Ruins" given to some of the ruins in the valley. Frederick Courteney Selous also visited the ruins and doubtless many others who left no record.

Baines.

Thomas Baines did not visit the ruins but this did not stop him painting them. It appears that he drew them from Mauch's description for he made some mistakes which would have been avoided had he ever been there. On the other hand there are other details not described by Mauch, so he must have had some other source of information as well.

The Posselt Brothers.

Willi and Harry Posselt visited Zimbabwe in 1889. Many years later (1924) Willi made a full description of the ruins in which he mentions something that Mauch overlooked - the presence of carved stone birds standing on pillars.

Posselt had great difficulty in obtaining permission to visit Zimbabwe but when he searched the Lower Enclosure he gave a description very similar to that of Mauch made eighteen years earlier. The next day Willi climbed the Hill Ruin where he found Andizibi, a relative of Mugabe, the chief of the people living at Zimbabwe at the time:

"Near Andizibi's hut in an enclosure which served as a cattle kraal I saw four soap stones, each carved in the image of a bird and facing east. One stone was shaped like a millstone and was about nine inches in diameter, and another, a stone dish about eighteen inches in diameter, had a number of figures carved on the border. The 'bird' stones were planted in an old ruined wall within the enclosure.

"I examined the best specimen of the four 'bird' stones and decided to dig it out; but while doing so Andizibi and his followers became

very excited and rushing around with their guns and assegais, I fully expected them to attack. I went on with my work and told Klaas (his Basuto servant) who had two loaded rifles to shoot the first man he saw aiming at me. By means of a native who spoke a little Sesuto - I did not know any Mashona - I was able to tell Andizibi that I had no intention of removing the stone but that I was quite prepared to buy it. This evidently passified him for I was not troubled any further.

"The next day I returned with some blankets and other articles in exchange for one of these 'bird' stones and a round perforated stone. The 'bird' stone was too heavy to carry so I cut off the pedestal. I stored the remaining stones in a safe place, my intention being to return one day and secure them from the natives."

Later when Posselt returned to the Transvaal, Rhodes bought the stones. Posselt's visit to the ruins has been commemorated by naming one of the Valley Ruins after him.

STONE WALLING AT ZIMBABWE.

J.Harris. 3A.

1. Style P.

The earliest style. Walls are comparatively thin with almost vertical faces. The untrimmed stones of varying thickness are often found laid on bare rock. Entrances are squared.

Complex Enclosures of Style P.

The north wall of No 1 ruin, north of the Great Enclosure, is perhaps one of the best examples of a wall built in this style. It rests on a solid foundation of rock having been built from stones quarried from local granite slabs. These slabs were split into layers by building great fires over them and then by cooling them rapidly with water: they split at right angles to the flat faces. The lower courses obviously follow the contours of the granite foundation slab; the builders however partly corrected this by adding false courses which meant that the top of the wall became relatively level.

One of the remaining lintelled doorways has been preserved in Style P walling. This is situated in the Western Enclosure of the Acropolis. This Covered Passage, as it is known, is probably the most sophisticated structure existing in any ruin in Southern Africa. Such passages are prone to collapse through neglect but floor remains suggest that they were not uncommon in this period.

This style also made great use of existing boulders, probably to save time and labour, and such use can be seen in the Western Enclosure of the Acropolis. These unmortared walls can further absorb shocks or movement with little danger of collapse - they are so loosely constructed as to be flexible and hence have remained erect for centuries.

2. Style Q.

This is a later style (15th Century) in which the stones are carefully trimmed and selected to form level courses. Although they have no foundations these walls were often laid in trenches. The bases are wider than the tops and the entrances are rounded. Some have slots in them which could have been for the insertion of wooden door jambs. Buttresses and steps belong to this period, as do towers, monoliths and turrets.

Complex Enclosures of Style Q.

The best example of Q-Type walling is the Great Enclosure itself which is almost entirely Q-Type. The inner wall of the Parallel Passage is an example of a collapsed P-Type wall which has been rebuilt by later masons.

The building of the outer wall of the Great Enclosure introduced more advanced techniques in wall building :

1. the foundation trench has a levelled floor indicating a possible levelling instrument;
2. the first course has been laid as an even pavement over the whole trench;
3. the facing stones have been carefully trimmed and the blocks have been selected for thickness;
4. all courses in the wall are level which indicates the use of a levelling instrument;
5. the thick walls have an inward batter which is even, indicating the use of a plumb line;
6. Style Q has wall patterns.

It is assumed that the wall commenced from the main or north entrance and continued in a clockwise direction. This can be deduced from the fact that the wall gets progressively thinner after the end of the Chevron pattern, indicating a shortage of stone.

The Conical Tower belongs to the same period although it is thought to be a little earlier than the wall itself. One theory suggests that the Tower was built by a chief and the wall by his successor, perhaps to construct something more imposing than his predecessor or to hide the Tower from outside view. Then if the architect of the Tower were still alive he would undoubtedly have been set the task of building the wall. Thus the same craftsman could have built the tower and the wall up to and including the Chevron Pattern.

The quality of construction deteriorates after the Chevron Pattern, about twenty one metres from the Tower in a clockwise direction. This could be due to the loss of the original craftsman and the continuation of the work by an unskilled hand who copied earlier methods without fully appreciating them. The same architect however may have been present but some event reduced his labour force which would have resulted in coarser stones and consequent deterioration of the wall in both size and thickness.

Decorated Q-Type Walls.

Variegated Stonework - sometimes efforts have been made to make a pattern in the wall by introducing bands of different colour. The effect is obtained by building several courses of dark stone into a wall of predominantly light granite. Such a wall can be seen just north of the Tower in the form of three bands of greenstone built into the main wall. On the other side of the doorway (next to the platform) the pattern continues in five bands of greenstone. There is no apparent reason for this.

Chevron Pattern - this is the most sophisticated and the hardest pattern to build. In the east wall of the Great Enclosure is a double Chevron Pattern comprised of two rows of opposing chevrons separated by a single horizontal course. This was even more difficult to build because it is nine metres above the ground.

Construction of Lintelled Doorways in Q-Type Walling.

The walling was built up to door height, about $2\frac{1}{4}$ metres, above the door sill. The entrances were carefully rounded and were made so strong that they could, and did, withstand severe batterings from collapsing masonry.

Wooden lintels were then laid. This involved the lifting of heavy timbers to a height of about $3\frac{1}{2}$ metres above the ground. The most probable 'machine' used to raise these logs of the pest-resistant Mutuvuti (Sandalwood) tree was an earthen ramp. Once the lintels were in place the earth was used to raise the floor level inside the enclosure. Blocks with air spaces laid above the logs would have lessened the weight they had to bear and the wall

Main (North) Entrance of the Great Enclosure.

(from R. Summers, "Ancient Ruins and Vanished Civilisations of S. Africa", p.135.)

in fact slopes inwards more steeply above the doorways.

Drains.

The architect of the wall was sensitive to drainage probably because he realised that a paved stone courtyard needed a run off for rain water. He built six drains into the north-eastern section and there are eight more known drains.

Most of these holes in the basal courses of the wall are roofed with stone but one which was roofed with timber has collapsed and caused the wall to subside. It was one of these timbers that produced a date for the wall (1380 $\pm$ 90.)

Sills and Steps.

When the builders of the outer wall discovered that they had a difference of between 60 and 80 cms in interior and exterior levels they built a very high threshold to retain the fill. At the north entrance the builders provided a flight of six steps to enable people to climb the threshold. There was once a similar flight at the west entrance but it has since been destroyed. Yet another was uncovered in the Parallel Passage and, like the others, it is peculiar to Zimbabwe.

Radial Walls.

These are best developed in P and Q Type enclosures. The enclosures have been subdivided into sections, the separating walls two metres high cutting off all communication between neighbours. There were some extremely low structures 80 to 100 cms high which appear to have been divisions in the family yard. Disconnections in these walls are thought to be the sites of collapsed huts.

3. Style R.

This is the latest style and no attempt has been made at coursing the stones as in earlier styles. The rounded doorways lack slots. Although most R-Type walls have collapsed, the Ridge Ruins north-west of the Great Enclosure provide a good example.

References : R.Summers "Ancient Ruins and Vanished Civilisation of S.Africa."
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Guide to the Zimbabwe Ruins, 1964

GREAT ZIMBABWE - WHO BUILT IT?

Philippa Wyrley-Birch. U6.

"We must give it up,
that speechless past;
Whether fact or chronology,
doctrine or mythology;
Whether in Europe, Asia,
Africa or America;
At Thebes or Palenque,
On Lycian shore
Or Salisbury Plain;
lost is lost,
Gone is gone forever."

Palgrave (quoted by Hall and Neal.)

Lost is lost and gone forever? ... Mr Palgrave has missed completely the point of archaeology. Man cannot live for the present or even the future alone. Surely those who have been before shed considerable light on the way we live? A study of history puts into perspective our political, social and economic conceptions; Zimbabwe is our heritage and the enigma that it presents exerts a dialectic fascination on all Rhodesians.

Before summarising some of the theories put forward as to the origins of Zimbabwe it is necessary to examine the derivation of the name itself.

- (a) Theodore Bent believed the name 'Zimbabwe' to be of Bantu origin, coming from the north. He thought the name was used generally to denote the head kraal of any chief.

'Zi' - Bantu root for village.
'umzi' - in Zulu denotes a collection of kraals.
'Zimbab' - signifies somewhat the same - "the great kraal."
'we' - terminal, denoting exclamation.

Hence, "Here is the Great Kraal."

- (b) Others suggest a connection to the biblical "Saba" of which there were three - two were in Southern Arabia, the third is not located. The river "Saba" or Sabi flows about seventy miles to the west of Zimbabwe. It is argued that the river acquired its name because of occupation by the Sabaeans from South Arabia. The oldest Arab records speak of the country of Saba as lying inland to the west of Sofala.
- (c) Some suggest a connection with the Zimbab (Owazimba, Monzimba or Cazembe) mentioned by Diego de Conto. These people, who were not vassals of the Monomotapa, occupied the land north of Tete. These people have been described as the Goths, Huns and Vandals of S.E. Africa, who devastated 300 leagues on the coast and entered Monomotapa's country. They were supposedly the "Abolosi" who piled up ramparts of unhewn stones on kopjes around Rhodesia known as "Abolosi forts."
- (d) Selous believed that Zimbabwe was derived from -
 'umba' or 'imba' - a building (plural, 'zimba') and
 'mabgi' - stones.
 Hence "a building of stones."
- (e) Reverend G. Cullen Reed suggests the name is that of the capital of the Mambo. Or it could be derived from 'ndzimu' and 'ibgne' meaning the "spirit of the rock."

Hall and Neal, "The Ancient Ruins of Rhodesia" (pub. 1902)

Professor Muller, an Austrian authority on Arabian archaeology, describes in detail the temple-fort ruins of Manibi, the ancient capital of the Sabaeen kingdom. Several archaeologists of repute, including Hall and Neal, (and refer too Zuro 1972, pp 11-15, address by Mr Latham on the WaRozwi) have compared this description with Zimbabwe and arrived at the conclusion that they were built by the same people. Using known Sabaeen history as a basis this would mean that the first period at Zimbabwe was built between 2000 and 1100 BC after which time the commerce and influence of the Sabaeans was absorbed by the Phoenicians. The second period at Zimbabwe would thus coincide with a Phoenician occupation (1100 BC to the Christian era) and indeed the style of architecture does resemble some of that of the old Phoenician colonies of the Mediterranean.

de Barros believed that the Rhodesian ruins were those of Roman forts of Agizymka of Ptolemy but today this is rendered unlikely.

The value of Hall and Neal lies less in their theorising than in their description of Rhodesia's ruins. The architecture they divided into four periods.

First Period.

- (a) Massive solidarity and symmetry of the buildings. The walls on the broadest foundations are approximately 5 - 15 feet wide with tops averaging from 3'6" to 7' in width. The summits are paved with granite slabs.
- (b) Decided batter back of the walls - at least 1:6 both outside and inside the main walls.
- (c) The main and divisional entrances and ends of the walls are rounded often having buttresses and intricate passages into the interior.
- (d) The walls are built on curves or elliptical planes. They are seldom straight.
- (e) The foundations of the main walls go down to rock foundations and follow that surface outline.
- (f) There are no rectangular main walls.

- (g) The workmanship is of the most superior quality. It is the same inside and out with no false courses. The walls are bonded throughout the width with the internal stones very carefully laid.
- (h) The enclosures are not filled in with debris and stones except in cases of reoccupation.
- (i) The finest granite powder cement floors are used. These deteriorated in quality and thickness with each succeeding period. The first was glazed and smooth.
- (j) Drains have only been found so far in first period ruins.
- (k) There are few steps.
- (l) The courses and conical buttresses with platforms on the summits are so far only found in first period ruins.

Second Period.

- (a) Not as solid as the first. Width less, sometimes not exceeding 3'.
- (b) There are less batter backs on the outside walls and none on the inside, eg. Khami.
- (c) Squared main and divisional entrances and ends of walls. The main entrances open directly into the interior of the building.
- (d) The walls are built comparatively straight.
- (e) The foundations frequently do not reach bed rock.
- (f) Rectangles are prominent and general.
- (g) Workmanship does not equal that of the first period. The outside is good but the inside walls are inferior and without design or decoration. Courses are not bonded and false courses are frequent.
- (h) The presence of rising terraces is evident - these are usually tiers covering the summit of the kopje.
- (i) There is a greater profusion of decoration on the outside walls and on the faces of the terraces. This decoration is elaborately carried out and is principally a check pattern.
- (j) No drains have been found.
- (k) There are granite steps which have been cemented over.
- (l) These ruins are often located on kopjes.
- (m) First Period buildings which are extended represent all the features of the Second Period.

Third Period.

True circular and octagonal buildings constructed of larger blocks and mainly protecting forts.

Fourth Period (Decadent.)

- (a) Small circular stone buildings.
- (b) Smaller enclosures. Often made of blocks taken from more ancient walls.
- (c) Poor imitation of earlier periods.
- (d) Buildings often erected on cement floors laid over the filled-in enclosures of First and Second Periods.

James E. Mullan. "The Arab Builders of Zimbabwe."

Mullan argues that two Arab peoples, from Oman and the Yemen, were the builders of Great Zimbabwe. He believes that there is no evidence that the Monomotapa ever lived there although attempts have been made to prove that it was one of his residences. Mullan bases this belief on the writing of de Barros in 1552 who noted that Zimbabwe was situated "in the midst of the plains in the kingdom of Butua, in the country of Torwa, near the oldest gold mines." de Barros further notes that the Karanga themselves did not credit the Monomotapa with building Zimbabwe - "The natives say that they (the Zimbabweans) are the work of the devil, because they are beyond their powers to execute."

King Solomon.

Attempts have been made to associate Zimbabwe with the scriptural figure of

Solomon. A man of fabulous wealth, there is biblical warrant for his building prowess. Over-credulity and an ignorance of Arabian folk-lore led later Portuguese writers to bring Solomon into the African picture, his link being with Ophir. This association was given further support by the early postulations of Karl Mauch but received a major set-back in 1906 when an archeological survey led by D.Randall-MacIver concluded that the ruins were purely African in origin.

The Bantu Theorists.

Randall-MacIver, Mrs. E.Caton-Thompson in 1929, K.R.Robinson, A.Whitty and R.Summers, all of whom have done original work at Zimbabwe, support the Bantu theory. "Examination of all the existing evidence," wrote Mrs Caton-Thompson, "still can produce not one single item that is not in accordance with the claim of Bantu origin and medieval date." The surrounding granite country produces a vast supply of building blocks as a result of natural exfoliation, requiring little or no dressing by man. The architecture, Mrs Caton-Thompson argues, is imitative of a pole and daga prototype - "essentially the product of an infantile and prelogical mind" obsessed with childish repetition. No corbelling, no vault, neither arch nor straight line can be found at Zimbabwe.

Carbon 14 dating suggests a post-medieval date although the sites of ruins were occupied for a considerable period before the erection of stone walls. Pole and daga huts were a feature of the ruin sites and research has revealed considerable evidence about the social structure of the tribes which, the Bantu theorists argue, built the ruins. A powerful central organisation, a despotic ruler with absolute authority, the rigid division of labour, wealth through trade with the east coast, developed political and religious structures and skill in the arts of masonry and pottery are all included in the argument for an African C14-16th origin of these ruins.

The inspiration for Zimbabwe may well have come from the Arabs; Roger Summers believes that the Lemba may have provided the connecting link. "The Lemba," he writes, "have undoubted connection with the Arabs and they may well have inherited some of the secrets of masonry ... it may be that the Lemba provided the technical skill ..." Their features are distinctly semitic and they are exceptionally skilled in iron, bronze and pottery. "The building of Zimbabwe presented many technical problems which the Lemba are more likely to have solved than the Venda, Karanga, Rozwi, Duma or other Shona tribes."

Peter Garlake, "Great Zimbabwe."

In this, the latest book on Zimbabwe, the author accepts the oral tradition that the Mbire, the first Shona people, were the builders of these ruins. The Mbire brought with them the Mwari cult - Mwari is the Shona supreme god of the cults of the mhondoro (spirits associated with ruling dynasties.) Mwari was supposed to be particularly revered at Zimbabwe.

The Mbire people were an immigration group and their advent is dated to the early fourteenth century, their 'firm establishment' being later in that century. Tradition has it that they were affected by a shortage of salt: The ruler, Nyatsuwba Mutota, sent emissaries out in search of salt in the Dande area of the middle Zambezi Valley. The Mbire people moved north conquering the local people and settling in the north, where Mutota earned the name "Mwene Mutopa" meaning "Master Pillager."

Dr. T.N.Huffman, in a review article published in the Dec. 1973 issue of Rhodesiana, points out that oral evidence must be treated with great care - it is doubtful, for example, that they go back some 400 to 500 years with any real historical veracity.

R.Gayre of Gayre, "The Origins of the Zimbabwean Civilisation."

In this, the most contentious of recent works, the author concludes that the Phoenicians were too early to have had a serious effect on Rhodesia but neither can it be shown the the Zimbabwean civilisation was so late as to fall within the period of Bantu settlement. He therefore rejects the Phoenician, Moslem and Bantu theories and suggests that Zimbabwe was the result of pre-Moslem Arabs, assisted by Indians, Ethiopians, even Malays and Chinese, all of whom came to Southern Africa to exploit the rich gold deposits. The ideas of the Bantu school he considers a set of distorted facts which have done "considerable harm to the creditability of prehistoric archeology."

Gayre believes that though the Acropolis may be far distant in space from Argyll in Scotland, it belongs to the same megalithic tradition - "and that tradition did not come from the Bantu of Africa." He argues that the dry stone walling, the 'temple', the chevron and herring-bone patterns are all commonly found in the buildings of Southern Arabia and the Mediterranean world. The names of the iron-mining tools found at Zimbabwe are Persian in origin - in fact Gayre draws numerous linguistic ties many of which have since shown to be suspect.

Rnadall-MacIver argued that htere must have been a native work force and that the "character of the dwellings contained within stone ruins and forming an integral part of them, is unnistakeably African." Gayre agrees as to the work force "but this does not prove that the civilisation is derived from them." The Alamites and Samites, he points out, lived in the same way. Remains of huts do not prove a Bantu origin for in Ethiopia the people lived in huts while public buildings were made of stone.

Gayre does not dismiss the myths surrounding King Solomon, the Queen of Sheba and the Phoenicians as being without bearing; indeed there is strong evidence for the early exploitation of mineral resources in east and central Africa. As regards dates Gayre settled on the seventh century AD as that of the building of Zimbabwe - too early for the Bantu and the Islamic Arabs. It must therefore have been, he concludes, the Judaised Sabaeans who were the principal force behind the Zimbabwean civilisation. As proof he submits the following table :

Comparative Table between the Awwam Temple and the Zimbabwean Temple.

<u>Awwam Temple.</u>	<u>Zimbabwean Temple. (Lower Enclosure)</u>
	<u>Construction.</u>
Dry-stone, unroofed.	Dry-stone, unroofed.
	<u>Plan.</u>
Oval, kidney shaped.	Oval, kidney shaped.
	<u>Height of Wall.</u>
9,5 metres	9,5 metres.
	<u>Wall Batter.</u>
4,12 metres at base 3,3 at summit	4 to 5,9 metres at base 3,1 at summit
	<u>Orientation.</u>
Main axis NW - SE Short axis NE - SW	Main axis NW - SE Short axis NE - SW

Wall Decoration.

At summit and only around $\frac{1}{4}$ of better built portion of wall. At summit and only around $\frac{1}{4}$ of better built portion of wall.

Religious Use.

Mother god cult embracing worship of sun, moon, stars and fertility gods. Symbolised in stone monoliths, phalli etc.

Evidence of mother god cult, sun emblems, phallic objects and stone monoliths, bird stelae, etc.

The almost identical shapes, orientation and dimensions suggest the source from which the ancient Rhodesian builders drew their inspiration. The Awwam Temple at Marib (circa 750BC) was the national shrine of the Sabaean Arabs for over one thousand years, a part of which time Southern Arabia controlled East Africa by ancient rights.

The difficulty is that Carbon-14 dates, many more of which are coming to hand, are aligned far more consistently to the fourteenth century than to the seventh.

Probably no one has the complete solution to the problem; in true Hegelian tradition each theory provides the thesis which stimulates its antithesis. No theory is useless; all are part of a continuum. Indeed what may be lost can be considered lost, but it is not gone forever. In the words of Robert Browning, "If a man's reach cannot exceed his grasp, then what's a heaven for?"

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SOME POSSIBLE FUNCTIONS OF ZIMBABWE.

T.Carroll. 4A.

It is likely that the builders of Zimbabwe had a function in mind for their construction although that function may not have been a material one. Furthermore one must bear in mind that Zimbabwe is unlikely to have fulfilled one function only - its uses probably varied although there is likely to have been one dominant purpose.

Some of the more fanciful functions suggested include an Arab trading post and an Arab centre for the colonisation of Africa. More common however is the use of Zimbabwe as a religious centre. It is thought that Mwari's High Priest lived on the Acropolis, hence the positioning of the Zimbabwe birds and the discovery of objects of phallic worship, the latter a feature of most primitive religions. The birds have not been identified (all the beaks have been broken off) but the powerful claws suggest an eagle of some kind. Monoliths and the Conical Tower may also have had religious significance; certainly it is difficult to determine any practical purpose for them.

On the negative side one should note that religion is not ordinarily sufficient stimulus for the building of something of the stature of Zimbabwe. Today for example the Mwari cult is centred in most modest surroundings in the Matopos. Nor is it necessary in African custom for the chief and the

High Priest to live in close proximity; in fact it is unusual for this to be the case.

Another popular suggestion is that Zimbabwe was built as a fortress for defensive purposes. The main evidence is the high, thick walls, the strategic position and the narrow entrances. However the highest walling on the Acropolis is on the steep east side which is most difficult to ascend anyway (the wall is far more effective as a wind barrier) whilst the northern side, easily accessible, is weakly defended. Furthermore there is a distinct lack of water for anyone besieged up the Acropolis.

The Conical Tower has been suggested as a watch tower. But why have a tower so difficult to ascend especially when the outer wall is quite wide enough to be patrolled?

Another theory sees Zimbabwe as the main link in a chain of fortresses stretching across the country. Signals could be relayed from one station to another by the use of fires in the event of the approach of slave-traders. Certainly there are other ruins showing similar building techniques to Zimbabwe but they are unlikely to have served the function described above. It is doubtful if the slave traders came this far south and if they did they would not have aroused the hostility of the natives thereby cutting off the source of the gold trade.

The idea of Zimbabwe as a trading centre is more reasonable. Accepting the Bantu origin of the ruins (and this after all has the most scientific support) the number of typical trade artifacts recovered from the ruins is interesting. They include beads and gold as well as foreign trade goods - Ming Dynasty china, North African iron goods, foreign beads, Persian ware, - most of which would have been carried by the Arabs. Although there are no ancient gold mines in the immediate vicinity of Zimbabwe there are the remains of a gold smelting furnace on the Acropolis.

Another theory connects Zimbabwe with the prestige of mighty rulers. If we accept that it was the centre of the Monomotapan empire, it is not difficult to imagine the structure as representing the power and might of the chief. The mighty walls, the designs in the stone work, the intricacies of the Lower Enclosure which would allow the chief to appear before the Conical Tower via the Parallel Passage without being seen, the Conical Tower itself, the mysticism of the Acropolis heightened by the presence of Mwari, all appear to be material constructions demonstrating political power. How readily would the primitive mind have been impressed by these magnificent structures. And after all, in Europe at the same time, Medieval monarchs were building their great palaces with the same intention in mind.

The concept of Zimbabwe as the court of the Monomotapa explains much of the other theories as well: the height and strength of the 'palace' in the centre, the possible religious overtones, and obviously this was the place to which foreigners would come to trade. The other Zimbabwe-type structures in the country of the same period (ie. excluding the later Khami era structures) would be provincial administrative centres to provide for the effective control of the Empire.

On Wednesday, 28th August, six members of the Society went to the Devuli Ranch to look at a Zimbabwe-type ruin. What was noticeable was the range of walling types - P, R and typical C19 Mashona refugee type walls - suggesting a long period of occupation. Was this, in the first instance, a provincial centre of the Zimbabwe era? Certainly its site is very similar to Matendere. It would then have been later occupied (in the C19th) as a refuge place against the raiding Madzviti' (Shangaans and possibly the Ndebele.)

AN EXAMINATION OF ZIMBABWE AS A RELIGIOUS CENTRE.

R. Plowes, 4A.

Zimbabwe has been attributed many functions and purposes since its discovery by Mauch and Renders, including that of being an organised religious centre. Mauch suggested links with the Ark of the Covenant and the Queen of Sheba which set off a chain of romantic theories! The interpretation of the ruins must depend on scientific investigation rather than speculation and thus information should have scientific or archeological backing. Another important factor to be considered in such an investigation is that - despite an apparent decline in culture - the mode of life, religion and associated activities of the modern Shona should be a reflection or indication of the Rozwi way of life. This would hold true unless it could be shown that some significant political, social or economic change occurred at the decline of the Zimbabwe culture. Thus we should be able to equate similar aspects of modern Shona society with those of the Zimbabwean era in an examination of religion.²

The most satisfactory general explanation for Zimbabwe is that it was the extravagant kraal of the great Shona Rozwi chief bearing the dynastic title of Monomotapa (Mwene Mutapa.) This chief wielded a great influence over Central Africa and had trading contacts with the Arabs and Portuguese along the East Coast. Suggestions have been made that the Arabs may have stimulated the growth of Zimbabwe.³

A study of the ruins and the objects found in the various places leads one to the conclusion that the well-decorated Great Enclosure or Temple was the chief's kraal or court. Here he would live in privacy and receive visitors surrounded by the Conical Towers and other such symbolic emblems of chieftainship. It has been conclusively proved by excavation that the Conical Tower does not conceal anything and must therefore be symbolic in function. Garlake draws a comparison between the shape of the Conical Tower and the shape of grain bins, suggesting the tower may be simply a sign of wealth and not have any religious significance.⁴

With the abundant labour force controlled by the chief impressive walling was built, its design and decoration constantly improving. Whitty uses the term 'prestige architecture' to describe the impressive building.⁵ This general interpretation of the Great Enclosure has been widely accepted and little religious importance has been attached to it for few significant items have been unearthed here.

The Acropolis or Hill Ruin at the time of the Monomotapas' inhabitation has been described as a sacred or religious place. Its function as a defensive structure is debatable because access from the unprotected north-eastern side is easier than from the southern densely walled approach which, as a cliff-face, is already sufficient protection in itself without the need of walling. Dr Huffman says that at present access up the N.E. side is impeded by overgrowth.⁶ It is improbable that the common tribesmen would live in such a remote place far above the water supplies and the fertile valleys below although huts from this period have been found. These will be discussed later. The Mugabe people lived in the Acropolis at the time of early European exploration but this was long after the decline of the Zimbabwe culture.⁷ Apparently there was no occupation of the Hill Ruin after the departure of the Rozwi until that of Mugabe's Duma in the 19th.⁸

The Eastern Enclosure.

By far the most important section of the Hill Ruin is the Eastern Enclosure although the Western Enclosure is impressive with its high walling surmounted by monoliths and turrets. A number of points indicate the religious significance of the Eastern Enclosure including the Zimbabwe birds,

phallic objects (figurines), an underground passage and the Balcony Enclosure, monoliths, acoustic effects and the general impressive design. Local tradition holds the area sacred and reports of early explorers, including Posselt, confirm this.⁹ Unfortunately treasure seekers, attaching some significance to it, ransacked this area, entirely ruining its appearance.¹⁰

Summers attempted to recreate an accurate description of the Eastern Enclosure based on archaeological evidence:

"Standing with our backs to the now restored curved outer wall, we may imagine we see to our right a cement covered platform several feet high on which stands a tall soapstone beam crowned with the figure of a bird; a little further round, against the base of an enormous granite boulder, stands a similar but larger platform bearing two or more pillars with carved birds. In front of us is a series of shallow cement covered steps or shelves stretching upwards and backwards to a cleft between rocks through which the sun shines for a few minutes at midday. These shelves are covered with clay pots - plain and decorated, some black, some coloured - with bowls and ornaments covered with gold leaf, with copper, bronze and iron ornaments and with all manner of other offerings. Well up in the centre is a small cement platform and lower down are some others on which stand great soapstone bowls carved with animal figures and geometric patterns; more steps curve up to the left leading out of sight to the Balcony; finally on our left, another platform on which three more bird pillars stand."¹¹

Although perhaps slightly exaggerated, this is certainly a vivid description and a good indication that something out of the ordinary used to occur here. There are two points about the physical structure of the enclosure that are of interest. Firstly, any message loudly spoken from the Balcony is amplified such that it can be heard in the valley below. A similar effect is said to occur with voices from the East cave, just below the Enclosure.¹² This phenomenon is due to the megaphone effect of the surrounding rock. The second point is that an underground passage has been discovered passing underneath the Eastern Enclosure. The purpose of this passage may have been to by-pass the sacred meeting place or possibly as a place from where mysterious voices were heard during a meeting. It is probable that the situation of the sacred area was influenced by the presence of these acoustic properties.

Interpretation of Archaeological Finds.

The controversial Zimbabwe birds are of much interest in a study of the religious significance of the ruins. They are the only sculptures of any size or complexity or displaying any attempt at representation from Zimbabwe.¹³ Apart from one found in the Philip's Ruin by Hall, all the birds have been discovered on the Hill Ruin, mainly within the Eastern Enclosure. The first bird was discovered in 1889 by Posselt and his description of the finds is interesting.¹⁴ (Refer article by B.Nicholas, "Early White Visitors to Zimbabwe.") It is interesting to note the importance attached to the birds by the locals.

When Theodore Bent visited the ruins in 1891, he obtained four birds on pillars, one fragment and two miniature birds:¹⁵

"From the position in which we found most of them, they would appear to have decorated the outer wall of the semi-circular temple on the hill. These birds are all conventional in design... From the number of soapstone pedestals with the tops broken off which we found in the temple, there were several more. Though they are all different in execution, they would appear to represent the same bird... we undoubtedly recognise that they represent hawks or vultures."

Bent concluded that these birds represented the 'female element in creation.' He believed that the build of the birds as well as the mystic signs carved on the pedestals indicated that they were vulturine symbols with a phallic significance. He suggested that they were evidence that the ruin builders practised a phallic cult; there is little recent evidence to support this.¹⁶ Summers has expressed the belief that the birds probably represent the fish eagle - hungwe - of Rozwi traditions.¹⁷

A total of nine birds, complete and incomplete, have been recovered from the ruins and were classified by Walton as being either 'naturalistic birds of the eagle type' or 'conventional birds.'¹⁸ A feature of interest is the carving of some symbol or animal form on the pedestal below the bird. All the soapstone birds have been intentionally differentiated by arbitrary and unrelated subsidiary embellishments.¹⁹ These carvings include representations of snakes, crocodiles and frogs as well as chevron and circular patterns, yet no two designs are alike. Possibly the Zimbabwe birds were an aid to ancestral memory; each chief portrayed by a significant subsidiary design which was distinctive. The Venda practise a similar procedure, using iron rods instead.²⁰

Walton declines to attribute any particular purpose to the birds although he sees them as having some religious function. He draws analogies with similar birds found amongst present Bantu tribes where they are used to ward off lightning and in association with herbalist/spiritualist ceremonies.²¹ With regard to their design Garlake suggests that they are stiff crude diagrams rather than attempts at realistic representations and says that they were not intended to be more than ideograms - 'conventional statements of a generalised avian theme.'²² Precisely what their significance was is difficult to determine.

Other suggestions as to the purpose of the birds include the worship of them as symbols of strength, or that the hawk or vulture was the totem - mutupo - of the Rozwi. Thus be it as commemorative gravestones, symbols of phallic worship, totem carvings or as decorations in the sacred altar of Mwari, the function of the Zimbabwe birds must undoubtedly be associated with spirits or religion.

Because of the facts that the monoliths were originally concentrated in areas that on other evidence had sacred character, Garlake suggests that they may have had some religious importance as they clearly had no utilitarian purpose.²³ Summers says that the monoliths are obvious fertility symbols as well as being evidence of the chief's power and role as 'father' to his people.²⁴ However Garlake feels that they may well have served as reminders or 'tallies' of the individual dead. His reason is that the dead have always occupied an important place in the Shona religion and it is essential for all to appease the spirits of their dead. The monoliths, including those carved with birds, look as if they may have been intended for this purpose.²⁵

Summers disputes the emphasis which Hall and others put on phallic cults. He suggests that many alleged phalli are only stylised figurines. Summers' opinion is that as agriculturists the Rozwi would be involved with fertility and consequently slightly concerned with human fertility too.²⁶ Discussing these phallic objects Garlake says that though such objects may have been childrens' playthings, their standardisation, considerable stylisation, restricted distribution and probable association with highly anthropomorphic figurines suggests rather that they had a symbolic or ideological content.²⁷

The sixty objects found around Bent's altar in the Eastern Enclosure are in fact highly stylised human torsoes rather than phalli. Their interpretation is extremely hazardous. They were perhaps symbols of a cult that

existed at about the middle of the present millenium. At Zimbabwe this cult appears to have existed with or even become associated with the ideology or rituals belonging to the bird carvings.²⁸ What these cults entailed is subject to speculation. Possibly they were connected with ancestral worship or the Mwari cult.

The mystery of purpose also envelops the queerly decorated soapstone cylinder known as the 'rosette cylinder'. Summers suggests that this was an ivory tusk holder but then one would expect to find other similar articles.²⁹ The final set of soapstone objects of interest are the flat-bottomed dishes measuring 13-21" across. They are probably utilitarian rather than symbolic despite being found in association with the birds and figurines.³⁰ Garlake feels that they may be imitations of elaborately carved items seen on the Arab trade routes. This is the type of superficial or even trivial influence that one might expect from strangers who had no intimate contact or any significant cultural impact on their hosts.³¹ These dishes, like the soapstone birds and figurines, may reflect the increasing luxury of the later part of Zimbabwe's occupation. If these bowls had any religious function it is not clearly evident. Summers points out that many of the animals carved on the bowls are in fact modern Shona totem animals.³²

A Discussion of the Mwari Cult.

The theory of the Eastern Enclosure being used as a giant Mwari cult centre because of its physical properties and the objects found there was originally suggested by Summers before any trained observer had ever seen a Mwari cult in action. When Daneel and Mwanza visited the Matopo centre, they discovered facts about the cult that differed considerably from the ideas of Summers.³³ For instance, the actual voice of the Mwari oracle is that of a female who holds intimate conversations with the people from a cave. Summers had suggested that the oracle spoke from the balcony with a commanding voice down into the valley below. This does not mean that Zimbabwe was never a Mwari cult centre, but rather that the theorisation of the early 1960's must be brought into line with the findings of modern research.³⁴ Thus Summers' theory must be adjusted to fit in with the facts and his basic idea of a Mwari cult centre could still be true.

There are many indications that the Rozwi worshipped Mwari or Mlimo as do the modern Shona. Oral traditions of the Mutapa house of the Zambesi escarpment and the Mutinhima house at Buhera claim that Zimbabwe was a Mwari cult centre.³⁵ Beach does point out though that it has been over four centuries since either of these Rozwi clans have had direct contact with Zimbabwe.³⁶

To try and relate Zimbabwe finds with the Mwari cult requires a basic understanding of the present day Mwari worship. The supreme god and creator, Mwari, influences, governs or controls many aspects of the life of the believer through a number of lesser spirits. These include the Mudzimu (a family ancestral spirit involved with protection), the Mhondoro (a clan spirit controlling crops, rain and fortune) as well as certain evil spirits (Shavi) and other spirits involved with fertility, disease, ancestors, etc.³⁷ The Mwari religion thus governs or influences many aspects of the tribal social structure and the individuals' lives. All problems and troubles can be associated with some aspect of this complex faith and can be solved by consultation with a religious spokesman or priest.

Mauch was the first to mention the Mwari cult in association with Zimbabwe.³⁸ The Mauch diaries, now fully translated, give a radically different picture to the original impression.³⁹ Bebreke, Mauch's informant, gave evidence to the effect that Zimbabwe was not the Mwari cult centre in the 18th and Mauch himself knew that the Mwari cult was based in the Matopos

Zimbabwe Hill Ruin

from Sumner and Hall.

Zimbabwe Bird
found in Philip's Ruin.

Eastern Enclosure

*showing arrangement
of birds - a
from Hall.*

Ceremonial spear
found by Hall.

Hills at the time. However this only tells us the position of the Mwari cult at the time of Mauch's visit and not of the situation during its major occupation.

Confusion arose from the observations of visitors, such as Mauch, of ceremonies conducted by Bereke's tribe every three or four years at the Hill Ruin. These ceremonies were actually simple grave rituals at which Mwari is traditionally praised.⁴⁰ Summers appears to have misinterpreted these ceremonies and presents them as typical of Mwari worship as practised by the Rozwi. He also attempts to link the New Year fire-lighting ceremonies held during October with the rituals practised at Zimbabwe. The event is supposed to be timed by observations of the star cluster Pleiades.⁴¹ Such theories as these are flimsy and have little evidence to support them.

There are indications that a cult similar to, if not the, Mwari cult was practised by the Rozwi at Zimbabwe. It is not illogical to assume that the Mwari cult may have evolved from the beliefs and rituals practised at Zimbabwe. Possibly Zimbabwe was the site of development of the Mwari cult and it was not until later that the Mwari cult as we know it was practised. The reason for this suggestion is that various religious articles, associated with present day Mwari worship, have been found at Zimbabwe and no satisfactory explanation for their combined presence has been suggested.

Where the chief lived, here too the tribe's god would be centred. It is therefore not unreasonable to assume that the Eastern Enclosure was in fact an altar or temple to a superior being. The huts on the Hill Ruin which date back to that time could have been the houses of the priests and their servants. The soapstone figurine ornaments may have adorned the temple. Those items which are unmistakably phallic in significance could show that an emphasis was placed on the fertility and sexual aspect of the cult. The Zimbabwe bird and crocodile may possibly symbolise the male and female attributes of the Shona High God respectively.⁴¹ One must consider that no such carvings are associated with the present day Mwari worship and therefore there are probably better explanations for the Zimbabwe bird than this.

It is possible that there was a close relationship between the chief and the tribe's religion although this is not noticeable amongst modern Shona. Paver states that "To the VaRozwi, their conception of the god Mwari had in it elements of majesty and power. In those days the Mambo (Monomotapa) and Mwari were supreme and of the two the god was the more powerful."⁴³ Of the same idea Garlake writes, "The Mwene Mutapa's religious functions, particularly as an intercessor with Mwari and the Mhondoros, were important and he was regarded as semi-divine to the extent that the welfare of the state was believed to be supernaturally dependent on his health."⁴⁴

Death did not terminate the chief's usefulness to his people. Through ancestral spirits he could still guide his people. Thus with such close connections between the chief and his god, it is not unlikely that the chiefs would be buried in the holy temple of their god on the Hill Ruin. No other burial ground has been found as yet because of the rapid decay of bone in the acid soils. The Zimbabwe birds may thus have been used as gravestones or commemorative symbols as already discussed. Should the Eastern Enclosure have been a burial site, it would explain the superstition of the locals surrounding it. In this regard Summers states "Chiefs were naturally buried in such a place and once a year the current chief and his headmen withdrew there to scour the graves and in due course light the sacred fire which marked the commencement of the New Year."⁴⁵ Again Summers makes reference to the fire-lighting ceremony of which there is no direct evidence.

There are reports of close associations of the Eastern Enclosure which contained many religious and possibly ancestral emblems, with the cult of

Chaminuka, one of the most important Mhondoro spirits. Gelfand says that Chaminuka was the voice of a Shona spirit under Mwari.⁴⁶ This alleged connection between Chaminuka and Zimbabwe needs more research.

A small point of interest is the gold or iron smelting furnace found in the enclosure next to the Eastern Enclosure. It is well known how much tradition and superstition surrounds the smelting procedure, especially sexually, among the modern Shona. Possibly the siting of the furnace alongside the Eastern Enclosure is of some significance.

Thus, although there is little evidence to prove the existence of the Mwari cult at Zimbabwe during the major occupation, we cannot say that it was not practised or did not develop there. However if Zimbabwe was indeed a Mwari centre as on the lines suggested by Summers, then the cult has undergone major changes since then. As previously stated Summers' ideas can be modified to suit the modern lines of thought.⁴⁷

Until further archaeological evidence and oral traditions are forthcoming, we can temporarily assume that the Eastern Enclosure may have been the site of a sacred oracle of the high god, Mwari. Here too the great Rozwi chiefs could have been buried. All aspects of the tribal religion including droughts, fertility, ancestral spirits, exorcism of evil spirits and problems of disease and famine were possibly dealt with here by priests and perhaps an oracle. 'Here was the meeting place of gods and men through the intermediacy of departed chiefs. It is the place truly called Dzimbahwe - the House of the Sacred Stones.'⁴⁸

In conclusion one must not imagine that the purpose of Zimbabwe was only as a religious centre. Indeed it was a great administrative, economic and social centre of a prosperous tribe and thus, inevitably, the centre of the tribe's religion. And at the end Zimbabwe reverted to what it had been when it first started, a place of great religious significance particularly favoured by Mwari and the ancestors.

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RADIOCARBON DATING AND THE RESULTANT DATES.

P.Nicholas, 4A

Who developed radiocarbon dating?

The initial development is undoubtedly due to Dr. Willard F. Libby who was the first person to demonstrate the occurrence of radiocarbon in nature.

How is radiocarbon formed?

The earth is continually being bombarded by cosmic radiation from outer space and this radiation is responsible for the production of radiocarbon. By certain reactions in the atmosphere radiocarbon is formed from nitrogen and secondary neutrons. It is called Carbon 14 (C-14) as the nucleus contains six protons and eight neutrons thus giving a total of fourteen nuclear particles.

Why is radiocarbon radioactive?

Because it emits electrons or Beta radiation from the nucleus - this emission causes it to change back to nitrogen from which it was formed. It is the occurrence of this Beta radiation which gives radiocarbon its name and enables it to be detected in the presence of ordinary carbon.

What is the chemical behaviour of radiocarbon?

The chemical behaviour (determined by the number of electrons) is virtually the same as that of ordinary carbon as both have six electrons circling around the nucleus. In particular it is capable of existing as carbon dioxide and radiocarbon is soon oxidised to radiocarbon dioxide which mixes with the 0,03% of carbon dioxide in the air.

How does radiocarbon come to appear in trees?

Since all plants utilise carbon dioxide in photosynthesis in order to build up their cell structure, their cells contain not only ordinary carbon but also radiocarbon. Because all animals, including man, eat plants (either directly or indirectly) they too contain radiocarbon. In addition all carbonates and bicarbonates dissolved in the sea become radioactive and thus radiocarbon finds its way into the whole of the biosphere, including aquatic life.

What percentage radiocarbon is involved?

The percentage is extremely small - one radiocarbon atom in every billion (million million.) Nevertheless it is possible by using sensitive equipment to detect the amount of radiocarbon. It has been shown that each gram of carbon (from a modern plant or animal) emits about 14 beta particles every minute.

How can radiocarbon be 'dated'?

Like all radioactive atoms, radiocarbon is capable of serving as a clock due to the fact that it decays with a fixed half-life of 5730 years which is unaffected by its chemical form, temperature, pressure or other extraneous influences. When a plant or animal dies, it ceases to replenish the stock of radiocarbon and it is the resulting decrease in its radiocarbon content which enables it to be dated.

After 5730 years the activity will have decreased to seven counts every minute; after another 5730 years to 3,5 counts and so on. In this way it is possible to date some samples up to 50 000 years of age after which the amount of radiocarbon remaining becomes too small to detect.

What kind of substance can be detected?

Theoretically any carbon-containing material which was once living but charcoal is generally used. This is because it is chemically inert and its radiocarbon content is not liable to be changed by chemical reactions.

The radiocarbon dating method.

About ten grams of pure carbon (an ounce of wood or proportionally larger quantities of materials with a lower carbon content) are needed for each test and two or three tests are desirable. This is burnt to yield carbon dioxide which is absorbed in limewater. The pure calcium carbonate is precipitated and dissolved in acid and carbon dioxide is again liberated and reduced to carbon. This purified carbon is spread as a paste on the cylinder of the geiger counter. The complete test takes a day.

What are the main difficulties?

These include uncertainty as to the exact half-life of radiocarbon, fluctuation in the radiocarbon content of the atmosphere, slight differences between the radiocarbon content of different materials and the error resulting from the statistically random nature of radiocarbon decay, an error which increases with the age of the sample. Other difficulties lie in the choice of samples : they must be of such a nature that contamination from outside sources of carbon did not take place to any extent after they were incorporated in the archeological deposit.

Drains, Lintels and Dates.

In May, 1950, S.D.Sanders, who succeeded Wallace as curator of Zimbabwe in 1948, reported the discovery of a piece of timber wedged up one of the drains which pierced the wall of the Temple. This was seen in situ by a good many competent archaeologists and in the following September, under Robinsons's direction, the Public Works Dept. opened up a section of the wall and removed what turned out to be two pieces of timber, both serving as lintels to the drain.

One piece was sent to Dr. Libby who had set up a laboratory in Chicago; the result was available in 1952 and found to be AD 537 (+ 160), a good deal older than Mrs Caton-Thompson's earliest date and far earlier than one which Summers suggested to the South African Association in 1950. Libby was surprised too and made a second and third test with consistent results, the average of all three being AD 591 (+ 120)

Mild consternation now reigned among Rhodesian archaeologists. However another piece of timber was still in hand so a sample was cut off the end, split in half, with one half being sent to the ever-patient Libby and the other to Professor F.E.Zeuner of the University of London's Dept. of Geochronology, who tested his piece by a completely different method to that of Dr.Libby. These two results agreed within the limits of experimental error and their mean value was AD 702 (+ 92).

This does not give the date that the wall was built, only the date that the tree died. One can say with certainty only that the wall must have been built sometime after the sixth century.

In 1958 charcoal was recovered from the very bottom of an excavation trench and gave a date of 330 AD (+ 150). A second sample from the debris of a later and quite unrelated people who lived on the Acropolis before any stone walls were built was dated 1140 - 1230 (+ 150). This suggests that Zimbabwe was indeed inhabited for many centuries (perhaps from as early as the second century) but that no stone walling was erected before AD 1000.

This evidence is strengthened by two further samples excavated in 1958 which produced dates of 1380 (+ 90) and 1440 (+ 150). The earlier was from a rubbish dump which ran under the wall of the Great Enclosure and which was formed when this part of the valley was occupied for the first time. It proves that the largest and finest walls of the Enclosure were built after the end of the 13th. The later date was obtained from charcoal lying on the floor of one of the last huts built on the Acropolis by the

builders of stone.

Problems.

When wood has been sealed beneath a considerable depth of impervious soil it may last indefinitely. But it is difficult to believe that equivalent circumstances can exist where the Zimbabwe wood was found.

J.F.Scholfield, the architect who supervised the preservation measures taken by the Public Works Dept. thirty years ago, made a thorough investigation of the walls, floors and foundations. In his "Zimbabwe; A Critical Examination of the Building Methods," he gives the clearest information available as to the level of drains and other features. Some of the drains, (which are merely rectangular gaps in the stonework about three courses high) were covered when the building was examined, but when built they were necessarily above ground. Their function was not only to let out rainwater falling inside the Enclosure but to carry off the water that ran down through the walls which are so openly built and so thick that large quantities must have done so.

R.N.Hall states in "Great Zimbabwe" that the lower portions of the walls were originally plastered to a height of as much as seven feet with a layer two inches thick. Quoting this Scholfield wrote, "It is evident that this would make it impossible for rainwater to escape, and it was to meet this difficulty that the walls were constructed with drain holes."

It seems impossible for the drain supports to have become thoroughly sealed even when covered by the debris of recent occupation. And it would have been precisely during the earlier period of the buildings existence, at the time when the drains would have been kept clear by the original residents, that any wood in them would have been most subject to frequent drenching by heavy rains, to the humidity which characterises Fort Victoris, and to the attacks of decay and insects to which wood in the open or covered by debris would be subject.

When the wood was examined carefully it turned out to be from the heart of a slow growing tree locally called 'African Sandalwood.' Trees grow by adding cells to the outer part of the trunk just below the bark and the carbon-rich material which forms the cell walls of the centre of the tree is thus built up in the early years of the tree's life. Perhaps these timbers came from big trees which had lived for centuries after the heartwood was formed. Again this tree has an astringent sap which can blind a man; therefore nobody will cut down an African Sandalwood - if he wants one he waits until he finds one lying on the ground and completely dried up. As it is ant-proof and practically indestructible a tree might be in the veld for a century or more before it was found. Yet again, how can we be certain that this wood was originally used in the Temple?

Further Tests and Research.

Hall mentioned quantities of nails and of "iron shoes and collars, once having served as bands round wooden posts," objects which might be expected to rust before the lapse of many centuries. Scholfield recorded that in the west wall of the Acropolis "considerable portions of the original logs were found in the tunnel entrance" whilst Bent noted that there were traces in 1891 of wooden lintels which had been damaged by fire. If there are any such remnants they should be tested. There is too the wooden plate carved with the 'signs of the Zodiac' found in a cave some distance from Zimbabwe. As the bowl depicted by Bent was damaged at one point, a further piece might be spared for the geiger counter.

To exemplify further the difficulties of radiocarbon dating, we were

told that the wooden lintel as tested by Libby and Zeuner has recently been retested and a markedly different and more recent date obtained! Radiocarbon dates are certainly useful but they must be handled with much care and discretion.

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Inter-House Quiz.

The inter-House quiz was run along new lines this year. Teams were composed of four members from each House (together with a team from UGHS) each of whom was required to submit to Mr Barnes a topic on which he wanted to be tested (ten questions.) Further to this each team had to answer twenty questions of a general historical nature; thus the maximum number of points possible for any one team was sixty.

The quiz was won by Palmer (43 points) from Hill (42), UGHS (34), Livingston (31) and Crawford (29.)

The highest individual score was achieved by Mary Armour (19) followed by Plowes (15), Wilson (14) and Gwyther (13). Both Tweedie and Ball scored full marks for their topic (10/10).

Headlines from History.

'Zuro' presents some events from the past as they might have been written by modern journalists:

BRAAVLEIS FOR RETURNING JUVENILE DELINQUENT.
 PHARAOH'S DAUGHTER EXPOSES "BABES IN BULLRUSHES" RACKET.
 MOSES ON SINAI GETS TEN POINT PLAN.
 BEN HUR TO ENTER DRAG RACE.
 RED SEA PARTED - ALL SHIPPING RE-ROUTED.
 CANUTE DOWN WITH FLU AFTER BEACH FIASCO.
 MARCO POLO TELLS OF RESULTS OF TRADE MISSION.
 COLUMBUS DISCOVERS FLIP SIDE OF DISC.
 LUTHER OUT! (See Papal Bull for full text.)
 NEWTON CONCUSSED IN ORCHARD ACCIDENT.
 GUILLOTINE BUSY IN FRENCH DISPUTE.
 DEATH OF ST.HELENA HOUSE ARRESTEE.

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THE WAR OF THE TELL-TALE AND THE BATTLE OF MHANDA HILL.

J.C.Barnes, A.Carróll, P.Nicholas, R.Plowes.

Oral traditions and Portuguese documents reveal that Manyika was torn by civil war between 1795 and 1875.¹ The leading contestants were the sons of Pfete who fought for the title so fiercely that Posselt² assumed that ritual regicide after three years reign was Manyika custom until in 1870-75 Tendai succeeded in driving out, killing or subduing not only the houses of the brothers of his father Matida, but also his own brothers. From 1875 to the present Tendai's house has dominated Manyika but this dominance was not secure for many years; indeed Tendai himself reacted very sharply to any attack, real or threatened, on his position. On the other hand the Makoni chief of the Waungwe³ was relatively stable in the latter half of the 19th. It was friction between these two dynasties, arising perhaps from competition to establish hegemony over the eastern Shona⁴ which led to the "War of the Tell-Tale" and the battle of Nhandu Hill.

Muswati, Makoni of the Waungwe and eldest son of Ruredzo, died in about 1835 at the time of the Nguni invasions under Zwangendaba.⁵ The next chief, Zendera, eldest surviving son of Ruredzo, was appointed amidst the chaos and carnage of the Nguni invasion. During the fighting many sons of Ruredzo perished and when the war subsided a period of drought and famine began, remembered still today as the "Shangwa". Taking advantage of the general disorganisation two men began to turn the population against Zendera Makoni and eventually killed him. The eldest of the two, Mukunyadze, became chief.

Nyamahindi, brother to Zendera, was in Manyika and was determined to revenge his brother's murder. He gained the support of Mudemberwa, Mutasa of the Manyika, who had married his sister's daughter. Mudemberwa sent his brother Matida to help Nyamahindi. The campaign was successful - Mukunyadze was captured and killed and Nyamahinde was appointed Makoni in his place.

When Matida returned to Manyika he found that his brother had been murdered by Chiefs Vumba and Zimunya⁸ and he was appointed Mutasa himself.

With the succession of Nyamahindi in about 1845 the Shangwa ended - the rains came and the crops grew - and for the next twenty years there was great prosperity in Maungwe. The most cordial relations existed between Makoni and Mutasa.

Circa 1864 Muzila, a Shangaan and father of Gungunyana, invaded Maungwe⁶ but was persuaded by gifts of ivory and karosses to retire. He returned the following year but found the Waungwe prepared and, with as much dignity as he could muster, he retired on the grounds that he had only come on a friendly visit.

Nyamahindi died in about 1865 and was succeeded by his brother Muruko.⁷ The following year there occurred an event that seriously disturbed relations existing between the Waungwe and the Manyika: Matida Mutasa was driven from Manyika by his elder brother Bvumbi. M. Gelfand offers an explanation for this move.⁹ Nyamondoto Mutasa should have succeeded by his brother Murahwa, but he was away hunting at the time. He was away so long that it was feared he must have been killed; hence Pfete, son of Mudemberwa, became chief. This was explained to Murahwa on his return and he was given a "nyika", today known as Murahwa's Hill. (It has the added advantage of acting as a buffer against the Hindwi of the south.¹⁰ When Matida became chief a man called Gowa (origin unknown), with Matida's connivance, conquered Murahwa. Bvumbi, angry with Matida for his part in this invasion, rallied his men and marched against him.

Warned that Bvumbi was on his way, Matida fled to Makoni who, because of the cordial relationship of the tribes in the past, agreed to protect him. Matida, whilst alive, remained a threat to Bvumbi. The manner in which Matida died remains a point of controversy, but certainly it was a violent death. According to the late Rev. Sells¹¹ Bvumbi gathered cattle and women and sent them with an escort of three men to Makoni who in return was to persuade Matida to return home on the grounds that his presence there was sorely needed. Muruko was loth to betray Matida but he was still more loth to embroil himself in a war with Bvumbi. Hence Matida was handed over.

As the return party approached Mutasa's kraal Matida was set upon and tied to a tree; a wooden stake was driven through his head and body, killing him and causing his teeth to fall out. One of his wives later gave these teeth to the deceased's son, Tendai, who thereupon determined to revenge his father's death¹². Bvumbi meanwhile had declared himself the new Mutasa.

Upon Matida's death his sons Tendai, Ziteya, Maparudze, Chimbadzwe and Charamuka fled to Makoni, but they were not welcome visitors. Matida's death had led to the establishment of two rival factions in Manyika - a pro-Matida camp centred on Matida's son Tendai, and a pro-Bvumbi camp centred on Bvumbi and his son Gwenarume. Muruko Makoni gave support to the pro-Bvumbi faction.¹³ Tendai was given temporary shelter by a sub-chief of the Maungwe called Tandi (who was also the usual representative of the Makoni to the M'limo.¹⁴) If Franklin¹⁵ is to be interpreted correctly a woman from this kraal went to Mutasa and told him where Tendai was concealed. Hence the name "War of the Tell-Tale." Bvumbi invaded, wiped out the kraal of headman Chendambuya and defeated Makoni himself. He failed to find Tendai but this was the beginning of incessant raids on the Waungwe

Tendai was compelled to move on and, on the grounds that as the son of a chief he wanted his own district¹⁶ he continued west to Svosve's country (Wedza) where he was related to the chief through his mother, Matida's wife.¹⁷ Svosve gave him men to fight after which he moved to Chief Zimunya, a relation of Svosve who lived in Jindwi.¹⁸ He also appears to have visited the Shangaans where he learnt how to use a bow and arrow,¹⁹ Saungweme, an ex-Shangaan and reknowned witch-doctor who gave him medicine to fight,²⁰ and the Portuguese, who encouraged the idea of an attack against Bvumbi,²¹ no doubt hoping to increase their own influence in Manyika.

There are two versions of the attack on Bvumbi. The most popular claims that Tendai and his brothers, living with Chief Zimunya, would make secret visits to Manyika mainly at night.²² One day Tendai met one of Bvumbi's wives in a field and won her over by promising to make her his 'vahosi' (chief wife) when he became chief. This woman made a fibre-rope ladder and, by hiding it in a bundle of firewood, successfully carried it to Bvumbi's kraal on top of Mt. Chirowarowa (not Binga Guru as is often supposed, although the two are very close.)²³ That night, after a beer drink, the woman let down the rope ladder from the top of the mountain (the heights were unassailable without a ladder; the regular ladder was drawn up every night) and the four sons of Matida climbed up. Ziteya and Charamuka were left to guard the ladder whilst Tendai and Maparudze went to Bvumbi's hut.²⁴ Finding the chief in a drunken stupor Tendai shot him through the heart with his bow and arrow.²⁵ According to custom he who cut off Bvumbi's head would be the new chief; Maparudze refused but Tendai did not hesitate. By means of drums found in the hut the new Mutasa was proclaimed to his people.²⁷ Incidentally he did not keep his promise to Bvumbi's wife: he felt that after her betrayal of her husband he could not trust her! and she was put to death.²⁸

Francis Pasipanodya²⁹ claims that the assassination plot against

The Chikanga-Mutasa Dynasty.

(after Beach.)

Bvumbi, involving a court woman (Mbuya Mataka) failed and Bvumbi fled to Makoni. His son, Gwenarume, was established as Mutasa during the inter-regnum until Tendai returned in force from Zimunya. Gwenarume³⁰ then followed his father to Makoni who refused to hand him over to Tendai and thus make good his previous betrayal of Matida. According to Baker³¹ Bvumbi's son Gwenanguruwe (sic) went from Makoni to P.E.A. where he lived in the neighbourhood of Chimoi at a place called Utewe.

Another of Bvumbi's sons, Chadeu, escaped to Portuguese territory³² where he obtained guns. He returned well armed but was beaten off by Tendai, possibly with the help of Gouveia.³³

The interference of each dynasty in the dynastic affairs of the other, especially during periods of succession dispute, is clearly evident. Nor was it one-sided - most of our sources are of Manyika origin and understandably enough emphasise the untimely intervention of Makoni in Mutasa disputes. Mutasa however could not refrain from meddling in the affairs of the Makoni dynasty - we know for example, of the aid he lent to Ndopfunya in the 1890's.³⁴

Nor were the succession disputes at Mutasa's court light-hearted affairs confined to the wrangling of tribal elders. At times the disputes became so acrimonious and hazardous that dynastic houses left for voluntary exile.³⁵ At another time the Mutasa was so frightened of succession feuds after his death that he carried out a policy of massacre against all heir apparents even to the extent of forcing young sons from the various Mutasa houses to be dashed down Binga Guru's rocky slopes.³⁶

But Makoni's dealings were not confined to intervention in dynastic wrangles; he formulated plans for territorial expansion northwards to Nyanhuka and east into Tsonzo. He wanted, he said, to eat 'tsenga' (an edible root plant) around Tsonzo.³⁷ Both Tsonzo and Nyanhuka were important to the Manyika for agriculture and frontier defence and were within striking distance of Binga Guru. One should remember too that the Makoni threats to Manyika coincided with the Shangaan raids.³⁸ To the Mutasa dynasty it must have seemed as if their very existence was in danger of subjugation by the hostility of powerful neighbours - Waungwe from the east and Shangaans from the south.

Rivalry between these two dynasties was further encouraged by another external factor, namely 'Gouveia.' Manuel Antonio de Sousa, (called Gouveia by the Shona although it is a name they tend to apply to all Portuguese of the C19th) an adventurer of Goanese extraction married to an African, the daughter of Makombe, had by the early 1870's established himself on Gorongoza Mountain and had begun to carve out a Portuguese empire for himself by subjugating the neighbouring African chiefdoms.³⁹ Matida had begun trading ivory with the Portuguese - not necessarily for guns but for beads⁴⁰ - and in about 1872 Gouveia made his first appearance at Mutasa's court to which he was attracted by the gold fields, ivory resources and his policy of establishing personal influence with all neighbouring dynasties.⁴¹ He offered cloth and guns in return.

In about 1885 Gouveia extended the area of his operations to Maungwe and made friends with Muruko to whom, it is alleged, he supplied arms and liquor in exchange for ivory.⁴² On one occasion he apparently exchanged guns for a bull.⁴³ He fostered Makoni's hate for Mutasa in the aim of securing for himself control of Manyika.⁴⁴

All in all it is not surprising that the new Mutasa, Tendai, having established himself in a new kraal on Binga Guru, decided to dispose of the Makoni pressure through force of arms.

The Makoni Dynasty.

After Abraham.)

* Mukunyadze (usurper)
1840-45

Enraged by Makoni's refusal to hand over Bvumbi's son, Tendai marched west on Maungwe and surrounded Muruko on Nhamburo Hill.⁴⁵ After a month Muruko, on the point of starvation and with the weather unusually severe,⁴⁶ was obliged to surrender but gained from Tendai an undertaking not to kill him if he retired to Nohwe, the country of Chief Mangwende on the north-west border of Maungwe. On the way to Nohwe however Muruko was persuaded by his kinsman Chief Cipunza to establish his kraal at Cinyudze Hill alongside his own kraal. Tendai, on hearing that Muruko had not fulfilled his promise, reinvaded Maungwe but was severely defeated by Cipunza who chased him back to Manyika and, according to Abrahams,⁴⁷ compelled him to retire further east to Johwe on the border to Utewe, although Tendai returned to his kraal several years later and constructed an unusual mid-river fortification at Chitungwiza.⁴⁸

From this time until Muruko's death in about 1889 Makoni and Mutasa carried out incessant raids on each other's territory. Mutasa normally raided by night; his routine was to cross the Odzi River under cover of darkness, set fire to the kraals of Makoni's people and rustle their cattle. These raids became so severe that the Waungwe there had to move further west and a no-man's land was created between the two.

Muruko retaliated by harrying those parts of Manyika along his eastern border. On one occasion he planned a combined operation with Makombe, chief of the Barwe people, by which they were to converge on Tendai from both sides at once. Tendai was pinned down on Nyangani Hill but, with the help of the Portuguese at Sena, managed to lift the siege.⁴⁹

The immediate cause for the Manyika invasion that was to end at Mhanda Hill is not clear but appears to involve a woman, Sange. According to one source⁵⁰ once Tendai was chief he turned his attention to Tandi who had been rude to him - during their previous association after the death of Matida Tani had taken a piece of stiff porridge from his plate and handed it to Tendai instead of giving it to him on a plate. As an appeasement Tandi offered to give Tendai a woman from his village. He sent for some young women and Tendai selected a girl called Sange who was either Tandi's daughter⁵¹ or wife.⁵² Tandi also provided some goat's meat for Tendai's soldiers. Tendai returned with his bride but as Sange bore him no children he became annoyed again and Tandi offered another wife, a young girl called Chinyama. In this account the quarrel ends peacefully.

Other accounts differ. Abrahams⁵³ states that Tendai's wife had run away to Muziti, son of Muruko, and Tendai used this as an excuse for paying off against Makoni all outstanding scores.

Machinwanyika⁵⁴ begins his chapter on the battle by commenting that "...one of Mutasa's wives fled to Maungwe for no reason and Mutasa became very angry about it and prepared an army to go and attack Nyakusakwa, the Maungwe chief".

Chief Makoni Muzanenamo⁵⁵ explained that it was a matter of Mutasa interfering in Makoni succession disputes. Gwasira, son of Zendera who was brother to Muroko, went to Mutasa to gain support for a claim to the Makoni chieftainship. Abrahams⁵⁶ mentions that Muroko had ordered an armed attack on Gwasira (correctly named Cinogomera) since he had aroused the jealousy of Muruko on account of his personal popularity amongst the Waungwe, after which Gwasira sought protection from Tendai. He did not however assert his claim to the Makoni chieftainship because he was vastly outnumbered by the families of Nyamanhindi and Muruko; in fact he did not return even on Muruko's death in 1889.⁵⁷

Whatever the immediate cause it was merely a spark which set light to a very combustible situation.

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The Manyika forces must have made their way through Tenya, across the Odzi Rover, along the Nyamajura River and reached Mhanda either by the gap near Mt. Zonga or by way of the Inyazura River to the south.⁵⁸ Once at Mhanda Hill they laid siege to the kraal of Muziti, who was Muruko's son. This kraal was at the foot of Mhanda Hill on the eastern side.⁵⁹ Muziti sent word to his father Muruko who was a Gwindingwe⁶⁰ and who sent forces under the leadership of Cingaira.⁶¹

At dawn, whilst Muziti was still asleep, Mutasa's son Chimbadwa and his warriors climbed up Mhanda Hill to watch for Muruko's forces.⁶² Franklin⁶³ states that Mutasa seized "a strong position on Mount Mhanda (sic).... which he fortified, "the implication being that Tendai's forces must have been on the hill much longer than other accounts would suggest. It has been argued that the battle at Mhanda was in fact merely the climax of a long campaign - if this is so none of the details of that campaign have been forthcoming.

As the Waungwe approached Mhanda, Cingaira fired a gun and called out "We have met".⁶⁴ Chimbadzwa, on top of the hill, realised that he was in a difficult position - he was cut off from supplies and parties attempting to reach water were fallen upon and destroyed.⁶⁵ He therefore came down to the ground and, in the region of Muziti's kraal, the two sides joined in battle.

Both sides had bows and arrows, assegais, axes, "swords" (big knives) and spears, and "a few" guns⁶⁶ the latter having come from Gouveia although it is possible that some were home made.⁶⁷

The early stages of the battle went badly for the Manyika - in fact they were on the point of being routed. Machiwanyika⁶⁸ gives two reasons for this, both interesting in that they are obvious excuses to draw attention away from military defeat. First, they apparently "broke their chief's custom that whenever they go to battle they should not be in touch with their wives because... it would bring bad luck." Secondly, it is claimed that the Manyika and Waungwe had previously agreed that, to avoid the tragedy of war, the soldiers "should not put bullets in our guns and only put gun-powder so that we may not harm each other". The Waungwe apparently broke this agreement, hence their success.

Change of fortune came with the appearance of Mutasa's ally, Saungweme from the Melssetter area. The reason for the alliance appears to rest in a truce agreed to on one of the Ungweme raids to Manyika when Tendai either gave Saungweme his daughter, Dzinga,⁶⁹ or, at the present site of Penhalonga, he married Saungweme's sister.⁷⁰

The arrival of Saungweme is rather mysterious. According to Abraham "he suddenly appeared out of the blue ..." ⁷¹ whilst others⁷² claim that Tendai, realising he was too weak to face Makoni alone, had sought the help of Saungweme before he set out on his campaign. Pasipanodya⁷³ argues that it was not the Ungweme at all but the dexterous exploits of Mutasa's crack Vaungweme units which, being mistaken for Shangaans, did the damage. According to Machiwanyika⁷⁴ at the time when the Manyika were beginning to retreat, Tendai was sitting down surrounded by some of Saungweme's people. As the Waungwe approached so did the Ungweme rush forward, their shields upraised. This caused confusion amongst the Waungwe for not only were the Ungweme noted for their skill with bows and arrows and shields but their appearance meant that they were mistaken for the much feared 'madzviti' (either Ndebele or Shangaans.) This "appearance" included knobkerries and shields, skins tied to the knees and ankles,⁷⁵ and the fact that they were whistling, as was the custom of the Ndebele.

What happened next depends upon the affiliations of one's informant.

According to those with a Manyika bias,⁷⁷ the Waungwe, in their temporary confusion, fell victim to the Ungweme and the result was an overriding victory for Mutasa. Makoni supporters⁷⁸ claim that, under the protection of the Ungweme, Mutasa escaped "by the skin of his teeth;" thus a victory for Makoni. We tend to support a Manyika victory, although not perhaps as decisive as they would have it. The Waungwe account tends to break down at the point where the Ungweme emerge; no-one can explain why the Ungweme, who were fresh and not yet used in battle, should have simply stood by whilst Mutasa escaped in disgrace.

But to return to the battle, which appears to have lasted for most of the day. The casualties were heavy⁸⁸ and for many years after there were rumours of the bones lying near Mhanda Hill. Included in these losses were four of Mutasa's 'magamba' (strong men, or generals) namely Gwazai, Muvungire, Nhepita and Tandii,⁸¹ the latter having fought for Mutasa since he was now his son-in-law. Shamunyama, another of the magamba, survived.

According to the Manyika historians⁸² after the battle Cingaira fled to his kinsman, Chief Cipunza at Chinyudzi. The rest of the Waungwe were surrounded in hills and caves until Muruko agreed to grant compensation to Tendai in return for his freedom. The surviving Manyika forces, led by Pfunda, Musewe, Matika and Murumbi⁸³ then returned to Binga Guru through Chiwanga. The injured were carried home, their injuries were treated with herbs by special ngangas and, as a reward, they were given girls to take as wives.⁸⁴

The general agreement between Makoni and Mutasa was that neither would encroach upon the land of the other. Mutasa gave Makoni his daughter Nyakanyikwa, who gave birth to Muradziki and Njera.⁸⁵ Makoni gave Mutasa a wife⁸⁶ and sent ten girls as a further entreaty.⁸⁷ Nine men taken prisoner by Mutasa were settled in Manyika and married off; two were called Joba and Mahokamatata.⁸⁸

Saungweme was given a piece of land called 'Gomo Saungweme' immediately east of the present site of St. Augustine's Mission - this land he settled until it became an area of white settlement.⁸⁹

What seems to confirm a Manyika victory is the action of Muruko's successor, Mutota Cingaira.⁹⁰ As son of Nyamanhindi, with whom Matida had been on such friendly terms, he was in a favourable position to approach Tendai with peace terms. The fact that it was Cingaira who made the first move is revealing, although one should remember that having just succeeded to the throne he was perhaps anxious to secure peace and thereby have a chance to secure his position internally. Cingaira sent his third son Zambi but Tendai, picqued that such a young person should lead the embassy, showed Zambi studied contempt by asking the latter to serve him beer, a duty traditionally confined to the chief's wives. Then Mutasa, satisfied that he had sufficiently dis-comforted Makoni's representative, assented to conclude hostilities.

This peace agreement was to be enforced in a way that neither Makoni nor Mutasa could have foreseen - the occupation of Manyika by the British in the following year, 1890.

References.

- (1) Dr. D.N.Beach; Generational Dating Systems for Shona Dynasties, U.R. Research Aid, p.16.
- (2) F.W.T.Posselt; The Banyemba Legend and Ceremony, NADA 2, 1924, p.11. Quoted by Beach, op.cit.
- (3) The Waungwe people lived in Maungwe and the hereditary title of their chief is Makoni.

- (4) Francis T.M.Pasipanodya; Seminaar Paper, UR 1971/72, Research project, Mutasa Chiefdom 1870-93: Some Preliminary Notes on Research; p.15
- (5) This account of the Makoni Dynasty, 1835-60, is taken from D.P.Abraham, The Principality of Maungwe, Its History and Traditions; NADA 28, 1951, pp 68-70. Note that Abraham refers to the invader as Swazi.
- (6) Abraham, op.cit. p.70. Described more fully by H.Franklin, NADA 1938, p.39, although he refers to the invaders as Matabele.
- (7) By comparison of genealogies it becomes apparent that Muruko is sometimes referred to as:
 Nyakurukwa (Rev. H.Baker, NADA No 2, 1924, p.85)
 Nyakurakwe (Franklin, op.cit.)
 Nyakusakwa (Jason Machiwanyika, Nat.Arch. MA 14/1/2; Lesson 13.)
- (8) J.G.Storry, The Settlement and Territorial Expansion of the Umtassa Dynasty, p.9; Paper read to the Umtali Regional Conference.
- (9) Prof. Gelfand, The Mhondoro Cult Among the Manyika People, NADA 1974, Vol XI, No 1, p.83.
- (10) J.G.Storry, op.cit. (11) Rev. Sells, a talk to the History Society, reproduced in Zuro, 1972, p.8. (12) Ibid.
- (13) Pasipanodya, op.cit. p.17. (14) E.G.H. NADA No.14, 1936/37, p.20
- (15) H.Franklin, op.cit. (16) M.Gelfand, op.cit. p.84. (17) Ibid. Note that Storry (op.cit) claims that Tendai's mother was a Jindwi, daughter of Zimunya. This would explain Tendai's later move to Zimunya.
- (18) Ibid. (19) Rev. Sells, op.cit. (20) Ibid. (21) Mambo Ininga, oral informant, aged about 90, resident Mutasa T.T.L.
- (22) Pasipanodya (op.cit) p.17 claims this is the origin of Tendai's name 'Chifambausiku' - he who travels by night. Baker (op.cit) p.86 claims that the name originated when Tendai fled from Bvumbi and became a fugitive. Abrahams, Sells and Mambo Ininga argue that he acquired the name because of the night raids he made on Makoni when he later became Mutasa.
- (23) Mandofa, oral informant, son of Pafiwa Mutasa. Also Newton, a Manyika and D.C.'s messenger - refer Zuro 1973, p.21. (24) Rev.Sells, op.cit.
- (25) Ibid. (26) Ibid. (27) Mambo Ininga, op.cit.
- (28) Gelfand, op.cit. Refer also NADA No 5, 1927, p.58. H.Franklin suggests that there was no appointment of a chief Mutasa - the issue was resolved by civil strife. He describes an atypical pattern which bears a remarkable resemblance to the murder of Bvumbi and succession of Tendai as described above. (29) Pasipanodya, op.cit. p.17. (30) According to Abraham, op cit. p.71. the son was called Pasinyore. (31) Baker, op.cit. p.86
- (32) Gelfand, op.cit. p.84. (33) Sells, op.cit. p.9 (34) Pasipanodya, op. cit. p.18. (35) Ibid. p.17. (36) Ibid. p.17. (37) Ibid. p. 16.
- (38) Ibid. p.15. (39) Ibid. p.19. (40) Gelfand, op.cit. p.83.
- (41) Pasipanodya, op.cit. p.19. (42) Abraham, op.cit. p.72.
- (43) Muzanenamo, present Makoni, son of Ndapfunya, born c.1900. Oral info.
- (44) Abraham, op.cit. (45) Ibid. p.71. (46) Franklin, op.cit.
- (47) Abraham, op.cit. pp71-72. (48) Refer Bate, NADA 1930, A Manyika Stronghold. Also Storry, op.cit p.3, and Rhod. Prehistory No. 12.
- (49) Abraham, op.cit. p.72. (50) Gelfand, op.cit. (51) Abraham, op.cit. p.72
- (52) Mabvurambudzi, oral info. age c.80 yrs. Resident Mutasa T.T.L.
- (53) Abraham, op.cit. (54) Machiwanyika, op.cit. (55) Muzanenamo, op.cit.
- (56) Abraham, op.cit. p.73. (57) Ibid, p.74. (58) Pasipanodya, op.cit. p.18.
- (59) Muzanenamo, op.cit. (60) Gwindingwe - also Makoni's kraal at the time of the Rebellion. (61) Cingaira - was to succeed Muruko as Makoni. Nicknamed 'the hawk', he was court-martialled and shot by Major Watt's column in Sept. 1896 for his part in the Rebellion.
- (62) Muzanenamo, op.cit. (63) Franklin, op.cit. (64) Muzanenamo, op.cit.
- (65) Franklin, op.cit. (66) Muzanenamo, Mambo Ininga, Mabvurambudzi, op.cit.
- (67) Mambo Ininga, op.cit. (68) Machiwanyika, op.cit.
- (69) Mambo Ininga, op.cit. (70) Mabvurambudzi, op.cit. (71) Abraham, p.72.
- (72) Mambo Ininga, op.cit. (73) Pasipanodya, op.cit. p.18.
- (74) Machiwanyika, op.cit. (75) Mabvurambudzi, op.cit.

- (76) Muzanenamo Makoni, op.cit. (77) Mambo Ininga, Mabvurambudzi, Machiwanyika, Pasipanodya, Gelfand.
 (78) Muzanenamo Makoni, Abraham, Franklin.
 (79) Mr. Lionel Makumbe, c.75 yrs old and a resident of Jindwe, claims his father joined Saungweme on his march from Melsetter and, together with Zimunya's people, was instrumental in defeating Makoni.
 (80) Mambo Ininga - "They died like locusts." Most informants agree as to the severity of the conflict. (81) Mabvurambudzi, op.cit.
 (82) Machiwanyika, Mandofa, Mambo Ininga. (83) Pasipanodya, op.cit. p.18.
 (84) Mabvurambudzi, op.cit. (85) Mambo Ininga. (86) Ibid.
 (87) Mabvurambudzi, op.cit. (88) Ibid. (89) Mandofa.
 (90) Abraham, op.cit. p.74. The fact that this comes from a Makoni informant is interesting. (91) Abraham, Machiwanyika.

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This project began as an exercise in the collecting, recording and interpreting of oral traditions, and there is still much to be done. We would like to convey our thanks to Mr Brodrick (DC Rusape) and Mr Fowle, (DC Mutasa) for their permission to work in the T.T.L.'s and for their assistance in laying on interpreters.

It was this exercise which formed the basis of a talk given in Salisbury to the Rhodesian Prehistory Society by Philippa Wyrley-Birch, Carroll, Nicholas, Plowes and Mr Barnes.

HITLER - THE LAST TEN DAYS.

In the second term the society showed the much publicised film, "Hitler - The Last Ten Days."

For some it was an interesting spectacle, but those who are familiar with the period came away disappointed; somehow something was missing. Perhaps the best explanation of this is found in a review by Michael Bellington which appeared in the "Illustrated London News" -

"... a thoroughly shoddy, second-rate film... As the title indicates the film concentrates on the last few days in the Berlin bunker. But, although dramatically convenient, this makes for historical absurdity since Hitler's decline is only significant if one has studied the preceding years in detail ... Moreover by sticking only to recorded fact, the film never offers any interpretation of Hitler's character or indication of how the private face may have differed from the public mask. And by casting Alec Guinness, whose speciality is his ability to project a saintly goodness and serenity, in the central role, the film finally squanders any claim to plausability. Significantly the only moments that work are those of black comedy: the nervous city official's inquiry as to whether Hitler is of pure Aryan stock when conducting the civil marriage ceremony with Eva Braun, and the avuncular concern with which Hitler hands out the cyanide capsules to his closest friends as a wedding gift. Otherwise it is a dismal film that leaves one with an inescapable conclusion: that it takes a genuine artist to comprehend a man of evil and that mere competence is nowhere good enough."

The film was banned from some British theatres. As Hannah Arendt said of Alan Bullock's massive biography, there is a danger of "a falsifying promotion to respectability."

THE ATTACK ON MUTASA'S KRAAL, NOVEMBER 15th, 1890.

J.C.Barnes.

With recent developments to the east of us it is relevant to consider just how close the Manica Plateau came to being included in Mocambique, and conversely the attempts made to secure Beira as a Rhodesian port.

The issue at stake in the Eastern Districts in 1890 was basically this: was Manica to remain the property of an exhausted nation or was it to be seized by settlers willing to establish a viable settlement? Portugal is undeniably credited with being the first European nation to invade this part of the world - by the end of the sixteenth century she had displaced Arab traders on the coast and established trading posts in the interior although no attempt was made at government. A series of military disasters led to Portuguese withdrawal from the interior but in the late nineteenth century feverish attempts were made to inject new life into the Portuguese dominions.

Dramatis personae were Major Paiva d'Andrada who founded the Companhia de Mocambique in December 1888 and established its headquarters at Massi Kessi, Baron Joao de Rezende, the local representative of the Companhia, and Manuel de Sousa, commonly called "Gouveia", a half-caste Goanese centred on Gorongosa mountain and a notorious slave dealer.

Gouveia claimed that in 1875 Chief Mutasa of the Manyika people had, in return for his having kept Makoni from attacking Mutasa, recognised Gouveia's control over Manyika. Furthermore, Mutasa was regarded by the Portuguese as a feudatory chief under Gungunyana whom, they stated, was himself a vassal of the Portuguese crown. To emphasise Mutasa's subjection d'Andrada in 1889 raised the Portuguese flag at the main kraal, Binga Guru.

1889 saw as well the granting of a Royal Charter to the British South Africa Company. The clause referring to the territorial jurisdiction of the Company was suitably vague but Rhodes was fully aware of the necessity of securing the Eastern Highlands and, if possible, a corridor to the sea. Instructions to that effect were given to A.R.Colquhoun Administrator Designate, before the Pioneer Column left Tuli.

Meanwhile on 21st August, 1890, there was published in London a Convention between England and Portugal, part of which agreed that the Sabi River was to form the eastern boundary of Mashonaland - ie. Manicaland appeared to have been ceded to the Portuguese. In fact those parts of the Convention pertaining to claims on the Shire River were unsatisfactory to the Portuguese with the result that the Cortes resigned and the agreement was never ratified.

Colquhoun, oblivious of developments in Europe, was preparing to carry out Rhodes's instructions. On 3rd September, together with Jameson, Selous and a mounted escort from A Troop of the BSACo Police, he left the Column at Fort Charter and made his way into Manica. On 14th September he signed with Mutasa a treaty in which, in return for a promise of British protection and an annual subsidy of £100 in cash or in kind, Mutasa ceded the rights of all minerals in Manica to the BSACo, gave that Company the right to establish amongst other things a Police Force and a British Resident, and promised not to make any territorial concessions without the consent of the BSACo.

The Portuguese were understandably furious with what they considered to be a volte-face on the part of Mutasa. Rezende submitted a written protest against this armed intrusion into Portuguese territory but Colquhoun, unperturbed and content in having carried out his instructions, left for Salisbury to arrange for the effective occupation of Manicaland. Behind him he left Trooper Trevor in charge of British interests.

A number of prospectors were persuaded to 'drift' into Manica and Sergeant-Major Montgomery with four men of B Troop left Salisbury as an advance party of the police force promised to Mutasa. Much to his consternation Colquhoun heard from Selous on 24th October that the Portuguese were approaching Mutasa's kraal with some 270 native auxiliaries. Three days later an urgent telegram arrived from Rhodes who, in the light of the failure of the August Convention, stressed the importance of occupying Manicaland. Reinforcements were drummed up and command was entrusted to Capt. (later Major) Patrick Forbes who arrived in Manica on 5th November. His orders were to protect Mutasa and, where possible, both to secure further territory under the concession and to obtain further concessions from other chiefs living near the coast.

The following day two messages were sent out by Forbes; the first via Lieut. Graham and two troopers to d'Andrada at Massi Kessi warning him that Manica was now a British protectorate and that British troops would resist force with force; the second went post-haste to Salisbury requesting further reinforcements.

The Portuguese, with their superior numbers, were not slow to act. On 8th November Gouveia, with about 70 retainers, entered Mutasa's kraal and raised the Portuguese flag in front of the chief's hut. He was joined on 14th November by d'Andrada and Rezende who, two days previously, had summoned the local prospectors - Messrs. Harrison, Harrington, Harris, Campion, Moodie and Maritz - to present themselves at Binga Guru on 15th November to witness Mutasa swear allegiance to the Portuguese. D'Andrada had told Harrison on 14th November that the Portuguese mission was to oust the B.S.A. Co. from Mashonaland and destroy their forts. He stated furthermore that he could cut off their supplies from the south and expressed sorrow for the "poor pioneers" should he have to bring his large forces - he had 200 men at Binga Guru and 30,000 more held in readiness on the Zambezi - to bear on them.

On the 15th November the prospectors were called into the king's private enclosure. Mutasa was cross-examined by Gouveia but despite his fear Mutasa refused for two hours to admit that he had, in 1875, given Gouveia an elephant's tusk containing soil.

But the British had not been idle either. As news of the planned coup reached Salisbury so reinforcements were directed to Untali. Victor Morier of the B.S.A.Co. Police, for example, whilst at Fort Charter received a despatch from Colquhoun ordering him to make his way to Mutasa's kraal as rapidly as he could - a fellow trooper and himself covered the estimated 157 miles in five and a half days. Being ahead of the wagons when the despatch arrived Morier had with him only a toothbrush, a horse blanket and two days rations - after the third day his meals consisted of monkey nuts and boiled rice. He arrived in Manica probably on 13th November.

Two other B.S.A.Co. Troopers, "Skipper" Hoste and Tyndale-Biscoe, were sent by Colquhoun to Manica with despatches for Forbes. On arrival they found, besides Forbes, Lieuts. Graham and Sheptsone, Denis Doyle (an interpreter), Baumann (a newspaper reporter), Morier and ten other troopers, and four ex-pioneers namely King, Mahan, Suckling and Ogilvie, a total of twenty one men.

On the morning of 15th November they moved from their camp on a riverbank about two miles from the kraal to the bottom of Binga Guru, meeting in the process further reinforcements from Fort Charter in the form of Lieut. Piennes and fifteen troopers. Shortly afterwards a native spy came down the hill to say that d'Andrada was at the moment trying to intimidate Mutasa" so we hardened our hearts and made up our minds to bag the lot while they were all

together." (Hoste).

The size of the opposing force would seem to be close to two thousand. Besides Gouveia's retainers there were about 200 Portuguese natives armed with Mannlicher rifles (but they were camped at the bottom of the hill). 1,000 of Mutasa's men and 500 from a neighbouring chief.

Forbes, Hoste, Doyle, Shepstone, Baumann, Morier, Palmer and Crawford (after whom the UBHS hostels are named) and about six men set off at 2 o'clock up Binga Guru, led by Jonas, a native interpreter left with Trevor when Colquhoun went to Salisbury. The guards of the three pallisades which protected the central kraal, thinking they were going to attend the meeting, made no objection and let them through. Once inside the British found a dense crowd of natives and, below the Portuguese flag, the three Portuguese who had just concluded their meeting. Rifles were loaded and with a rush the Portuguese were surrounded and informed of their arrest for "conspiracy and tampering with the natives of our territory." D'Andrada exclaimed that he was under the Portuguese flag but as he gesticulated one of the troopers broke the flagstaff, very nearly hitting d'Andrada as it fell. "At this point," wrote Hoste, "his language became unprintable: however....we made a prisoner of him."

Forbes pointed a revolver at Rezende and told him to put up his hands but Gouveia, whom Hoste describes as a big heavy man, made a bolt for it. Shepstone, only seventeen years of age, grabbed the slack of his trousers as he disappeared behind a hut; Hoste, seeing Shepstone being dragged along, raced around the other side of the hut and pointed his revolver at Gouveia at which he quietly surrendered.

What did the Africans do? Not much. Mutasa's men got it into their heads that their chief was to be arrested too and "began humming like a hive of angry bees," closing in on the party and flashing their assegais and knobkerries. Doyle (the interpreter), either with the co-operation of Mutasa's chief induna or having first cowed the induna, placed himself in front of the natives and, shouting at the top of his voice, told them that the new arrivals were friends who had come to deliver them from the Portuguese. As the mob wavered Forbes' men retreated through the gap in the stockade. Gouveia stuck fast and while two troopers pulled from the front Hoste placed his foot "against the blunt end" and pushed.

The moral results of this coup were tremendous, the news spread that the much-feared Gouveia had been captured so easily by a handful of British Police.

What was happening meanwhile at the foot of the mountain? Fifteen minutes after Forbes' party had left to climb Binga Guru, Fiennes, Tyndale-Biscoe and about twenty men went up the valley to where 200 armed natives - bearers for the Portuguese - were camped. When they saw the British approaching they rushed to their arms only to run up the sides of the valley amongst the rocks. Not having enough men to go after them Fiennes waited for two hours, took eight guns off those whom he persuaded to come down, collected a few sheep and fowls and returned to camp where they found three very disconsolated Portuguese prisoners.

Hoste offered the captives drink - both Rezende and d'Andrada refused but Gouveia accepted with the comment, "I am a prisoner and it is your duty to be kind to me".

Later Forbes entered the hut and was formally introduced to d'Andrada. "... up jumped the gallant Colonel, every hair in his head and beard bristling, and shouted at the top of his voice: 'Captain Forbes, you are ore damn rascal. In the future the very dogs in the street will bark when your name is mentioned.'"

Morier, who could speak Portuguese, was asked to wait at a table so that the British could later find out what their prisoners talked about. Apparently no sooner had they sat down than d'Andrada commented to Rezende, "This is like feeding in a robbers' cavern. And look at the brutes - eating with their fingers!" The last part of this speech, wrote Hoste, was "distinctly unkind since we had given up all our mess-traps to the prisoners ..."

The next day Rezende was kept at camp and was eventually released but d'Andrada and Gouveia were sent first to Salisbury and then to Portugal via Cape Town. Major Leonard described meeting the latter two at Tuli in December, travelling with Mundell as escort. D'Andrada he described as "a gentleman and very nice fellow" and "naturally very indignant ... and in anticipation of the rumpus he is contemplating, converts himself into an insensate fury on a hot day, and at the risk of bursting a blood vessel." Gouveia on the other hand, "was dressed in a striped sleeping-suit of various colours and appeared to be rather a retiring, mild-mannered half-caste gentleman - a thorough-bred Goanese; a class of people that were sometimes employed as cooks or boys in India, who make a great show of being Catholics and Christians, and a great show of being Europeans; ..."

Immediately after the departure of the Portuguese from Manica a meeting was called of the principal Europeans in the place - five Englishmen and a Frenchman. The English were pleased with the coup but the Frenchman refused to acknowledge British sovereignty and was therefore made prisoner.

Forbes had furthermore asked Mutasa for an explanation of his conduct. At one o'clock the chief came down with some 800 of his men. "In a most pitiable state of funk and dead drunk into the bargain," he was given a severe 'wiggling' after which, speaking through his induna, he assured Forbes of his friendship and thanked him for the presents of blankets and calico.

In the afternoon Baumann and Tyndale-Biscoe went to have another look at the kraal which, they concluded, was potentially a very strong defensive site. They met a few Englishmen who showed them where twenty guns belonging to Gouveia were hidden - these were confiscated and carried down to the camp by natives.

On November 17th a party left for the Portuguese fort at Massi Kessi. With the rutted terrain and the road in poor condition the twenty two miles took almost three days to complete, and that only after the wagon had been left behind and the horses led on foot. Late in the morning of 19th November the fort came into site. A couple of bastions looked as if they might have guns mounted on them and native sources reported that a Portuguese regiment had moved in a couple of days previously, thus caution was the order of the day. A messenger approached however to say that the garrison was prepared to capitulate - it consisted of a corporal and private of Cazadores with a motley collection of Portuguese, French, Spaniards and half-castes, mostly miners, amounting to about forty five. The fort was thereupon occupied, the Portuguese flag lowered and replaced with a Union Jack.

What were the objectives of the next move? Hoste's diary claims that the officers decided that "as the Portuguese had been creating trouble in our territory it behoved us to retaliate." Tyndale-Biscoe's diary is of a more innocent nature - Forbes was to leave for Beira via the Pungwe

"to arrange with the different chiefs about a road and Doyle left for the south for the same purpose." According to Morier the purpose was simply to "make treaties with all the native chiefs" - what kind of treaties he does not specify. More to the point however, is a letter written by Morier to his father on 13th November (ie. two days before the coup) in which he states "the Company ... have determined to annex (Manica), make a rush to the coast and gain possession of a seaport."

On 21st November Forbes, Doyle, Montgomery, Morier, Baumann and some troopers headed for the coast. After fifty miles covered in two days they abandoned their horses as they had entered tsetse-fly country - but most of the animals were to die anyway.

Hoste had been left in charge of Fort Massi Kessi with Tyndale-Biscoe, a sergeant and four men - and prisoners who outnumbered him 10:1, a ratio which increased when Tyndale-Biscoe left later in the day in an attempt to find an alternative route from Fort Hill which wagons could use. On 23rd he and Montague found a pass in the mountains; Capt. Bruce and a party of BSACo. Police were sent to cut the road and camped in the middle of the pass on Christmas Eve, spending Christmas Day there. Hence the name of the pass.

Let us return however to the fort. Several days after Forbes's departure a Portuguese soldier arrived with a letter from the Governor of the Province in which, after calling Hoste a number of names such as 'Saxon Pirate' and 'Norman Robber' he warned that if the fort was not evacuated Hoste would be hanged as a pirate. But, the soldier explained, the Governor and one officer had been left stranded by the desertion of the Portuguese force. Hoste therefore replied with a very official letter warning the Governor, in the interests of peace, to keep away from the fort. No more was heard of the matter.

On November 24th a sergeant and ten men arrived; Hoste put them to work on an inventory of all the stores in the fort, which he asked Rezende to verify. "Oh, you English," responded the Baron. "You come here and steal our country and then make a fuss about a few picks and shovels!" Three days later Rezende and the rest of the prisoners were released and set off for the coast, the Baron threatening to find Forbes and 'smash him up.' Hoste remarked drily, "I was not particularly anxious about Forbes."

A native runner arrived at the fort on 3rd December with a message from Forbes to the effect that he had established a station at Chinoio where he was leaving two men as a connecting link. He also reported the loss of the newspaper reporter Baumann - he had stopped to tie a bootlace, the column had gone on and had not missed him until breakfast: it was presumed he was taken by a lion.

The march was not an easy one. Morier, who was not one to complain, wrote "... we had an awful time ... I hope never to make such another trip." Almost barefoot and with clothing in tatters, the party was covering between twenty five and thirty miles a day in hot, steamy, tropical conditions, and until they came into the game region there was nothing to eat but Kaffir Corn.

On 29th November, within fifty miles of Beira and very close to the Pungwe down which Forbes planned to sail in native canoes, an urgent despatch arrived from the Administrator ordering Forbes's immediate return. (This despatch had passed through Massi Kessi marked 'To be forwarded to Capt. Forbes at any expense of men and horses.' Hoste later remarked that "if I had known what it was about I should have been sorely tempted to delay it, I fear.") Nevertheless the march was stopped and Forbes set off back to Salisbury, leaving Morier as interpreter and Lt. Bruce with ten men in charge.

Why the sudden reversal? The answer lies in the European diplomatic situation. After the failure of the Convention, Britain made fresh overtures to the new Portuguese ministry; on 14th November (ie. one day before Forbes's attack on the kraal) the Portuguese and British ministries concluded an interim 'modus vivendi' on a basis of the status quo whilst a new and decisive treaty was drawn up to settle the boundary once and for all. Under this modus vivendi the Portuguese rightly assumed that the Sabi River was still their western boundary - that is Manicaland was well within their sphere of influence. In the light of this the occupation of Beira by British forces would create an international incident with Britain seriously in the wrong.

News of the modus vivendi reached Colquhoun in Salisbury on 23rd November, hence his urgent withdrawal of Forbes. Rhodes, who was not to be hauled by matters of European diplomacy, sent a telegram to Colquhoun asking the Administrator to see to the occupation of Beira but it arrived in Salisbury only on 14th December, too late to affect the issue. Rhodes, incidentally, was furious with Colquhoun for the withdrawal of Forbes and this does much to explain Colquhoun's supersession by Jameson as Administrator of the new country.

The rest can be briefly told. The news of the arrests at Mutasa's kraal caused a popular furore in Lisbon. Two separate Portuguese envoys to Massi Kessi (Bettencourt and Freire) were rebuffed as an 'army of revenge' was formed in the Portuguese provinces. The Pungwe River was closed to everyone connected with the BSACo and on 5th May, 1891, a Portuguese detachment re-occupied Massi Kessi. The stage was set for the battle of Chua Hill, a two hour engagement on 11th May in which Capt. Heyman and about fifty Police and volunteers repelled about 400 Portuguese troops. Lieut. Fiennes led a patrol in pursuit of the Portuguese but only to find the missing blocks of some captured machine guns and so make them serviceable. It was in the process of pursuit that Fiennes heard from Bishop Knight-Bruce of renewed peace negotiations between the English and Portuguese. On July 3rd, 1891, the Treaty of Lisbon was formally ratified by both powers - the boundary was to include the whole of the eastern plateau in Rhodesia but if necessary it was to "be deflected so as to leave Mutasa in the British sphere and Massi Kessi in the Portuguese."

Portuguese anger has still not fully subsided. I believe there was a Portuguese protest over the naming of the relatively new customs house the Forbes Border Post.

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Nursery Rhymes. Georgey Porgey.

George I of England (1714-27) was surrounded by foreign mistresses but often proved fickle, thus he "kissed the girls and made them cry."

THE WARSAW GHETTO.

Philippa Wyrley-Birch.

In his speech to the Reichstag on January 30, 1939, Hitler said: "If the international Jewish financiers should again succeed in plunging the nations into a world war the result will be ... the annihilation of the Jewish Race throughout Europe". By the beginning of 1942 the time had come, as Heydrich said, "to clear up the fundamental problems of the 'final solution' of the Jewish question". This entailed the extermination of Jewry. Heydrich well knew that Goering meant to concentrate all the Jews in the ghettos of the large cities, where it would be easy to dispatch them to their final fate.

On September 13th, 1940, Frank had issued a general order for "residence restriction", that is to say, for the creation of the ghettos. Responsibility for their establishment and supervision was at first vested in civilian authorities but from October until November the Warsaw Ghetto was built - the S.S. seemed to be striving to have the Jews under their exclusive control.

It was noted how resigned the Jews seemed when they met their deaths in the Nazi gas chambers or in the great execution pits of the Einsatz squads. Not all the Jews, however, submitted so gently. In the spring of 1943, some 60,000 Jews, walled up in the Warsaw Ghetto, turned on their Nazi tormentors and fought.

By the late summer of 1940 the S.S. had rounded up about 400,000 Jews and sealed them off within a high wall from the rest of Warsaw in an area about two and a half miles long and one mile wide surrounding the medieval ghetto. This district normally housed 140,000 but overcrowding was the least of their problems. Governor Frank refused to allot enough food to keep even half of them alive - some 100,000 Jews tried to survive on a bowl of soup a day, often boiled from straw. It was a losing struggle for life.

But the ghetto population did not die fast enough to suit Himmler. Between July 22 and October 3rd, about 310,322 Jews were transported to extermination camps where they were gassed. This still was not deemed satisfactory. Himmler ordered the 60,000 Jews still alive to be "resettled" by February 15th. The severe winter and demands of the Army made it difficult for the S.S. to obtain the necessary trains to carry out these orders. The Jews were also reported to be resisting their resettlement in every possible way. It was not until spring that Himmler's order could be carried out, presumably taking three days. In fact the process took four weeks.

The deportation of over 300,000 Jews had enabled the Germans to reduce the size of the ghetto. On April 19th, 1943, General Stroop turned his tanks, artillery, flame throwers and dynamite squads on an area merely 1000 by 300 yards in extent. The desperate Jews had converted sewers, vaults and cellars into fortified posts, arming themselves with a few pistols and rifles, about two dozen machine guns that had been smuggled in and home-made grenades.

Stroop had 2090 men who ran into unexpected resistance the first day and had to withdraw. They renewed their attack but found the going heavy, losing 12 men. So it went on for a few days, the poorly armed Jews giving ground before the attacks of tanks and flame throwers but keeping up their resistance.

Stroop could not understand why "this trash and subhumanity" would not give up and submit to being liquidated. As time went by it became more difficult to capture the bandits and again new battle groups consisting of about 40 men and women kindled new resistance.

On the fifth day of battle, Himmler ordered Stroop to "comb-out" the ghetto "with the greatest severity and relentless tenacity". Stroop decided to set every block on fire. Many men and women seemed to surrender themselves to the flames preferring that to "peacefully dying in gas chambers". About 1330 Jews were pulled from dugouts and destroyed; 362 were killed in battle. On April 25th, only 30 were "evacuated".

Towards the end of the rebellion the defenders took to the sewers where Stroop tried to flush them out by flooding the mains. The Jews managed to stop the flow of water. Smoke bombs were then dropped into the sewers but they failed to have the desired results.

For a month the cornered Jews fought with reckless courage. By April 26th Stroop reported that many were "going insane from the heat, the smoke and the explosions". That day several more blocks were burned down. "This is the only and final method" he reported, "which forces this trash and subhumanity to the surface".

The last day was May 16th. That day 180 were destroyed when the Warsaw Synagogue was blown up. Sixteen Germans were killed during the rebellion and some ninety wounded, according to Stroop's somewhat hazy arithmetic. The figures were kept low as not to disturb Himmler's fine sensibilities. Stroop concluded that the German troops and police "fulfilled their duty indefatigably in faithful comradeship and stood together as exemplary models of soldiers".

"The final solution" as a phrase crept with increasing frenzy into the vocabulary of the leading Nazis, its seeming innocence apparently sparing these men the pain of reminding each other what it meant. At the Nuremberg trials most of the Nazi Chiefs denied that they knew what it meant. In their presumed ignorance over six million Jews were killed, either in extermination camps, in the ghettos, by medical experiments or by the Einsatz squads.

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CHARLES A. LINDBERGH, 1902-74.

S.Gilmour. 16.

Charles Augustus Lindbergh, nicknamed 'Slim' and six foot three inches tall, was only twenty five when he began a new epoch in aviation history by single-handedly flying non-stop across the Atlantic in just over thirty three hours. He remained a popular hero until the outbreak of W.W.II when he openly voiced support for the Nazis with his widely-publicised statement, "pressing this country towards war are the British, the Jews and the Roosevelt administration." His following was revived when he flew over fifty combat missions in the Pacific, but after his biographical film in 1954 (starring James Stewart at the zenith of his fame) it was obvious that he was a forgotten figure. In a survey conducted as to why the film was a failure, it was discovered that nobody under thirty had heard of him, very few people under forty remembered him and those that had didn't care.

Born in February, 1902, in Detroit, Charles's formal education ended after two years of studying engineering. He enrolled at the Nebraska Aircraft Corporation's flying school, which turned out to have one plane,

one instructor and now one pupil. After a few hours instruction the school received a good offer for its plane and closed down, forcing Charles to team up with a local stunt pilot. With no licence and never having flown solo, he bought a 90 hp Curtiss Jennie for \$500 and a parachute for \$25 and became a 'barnstormer', flying throughout the country. Joining the air service of the War Department in Texas in March 1924 (mainly because he could get so much free flying) he became an airmail pilot in 1926, flying the route between St. Louis and Chicago.

During this period he obtained financial backing from St. Louis business men to compete for the \$25 000 prize offered by Raymond Orteig for the first non-stop New York to Paris flight. His plane, the 'Spirit of St. Louis', was built by a small, new company because all major companies refused to take the risk of endangering their reputations on such a foolhardy project. When the Ryan monoplane was completed Lindbergh flew from San Diego to New York between 10th and 12th May, 1927, setting a new overland record, a feat which did not even reach newspaper headlines.

To cross the Atlantic non-stop was received by most people as an impossible task. Six people had been killed and three seriously injured in previous attempts. One plane had carried 9000 lbs of fuel; Lindbergh's plane complete weighed only 5250 lbs. To reduce weight all heavy equipment, including the radio, had been removed leaving only an earth inductor compass and an over-size fuel tank which completely obscured his forward view. Therefore a periscope was installed.

At 7.52 am on May 20th, 1927, Lindbergh left Roosevelt airfield in a plane which was small in comparison to other available aircraft and which had a top speed of only 129 m.p.h. Basing his navigation on the arc of a Great Circle, he had to judge the side drift of his machine and guess his way round fog and storm centres. Once Newfoundland was behind him, Lindbergh had to rely on his own navigation and the fisherman on whom he descended, put his head out of the window and shouted, "Is this the way to Ireland?" At 10 pm Paris time he landed at Le Bourget, ravenous because during the 33 hour flight he had eaten all his food - a quart of water and five sandwiches.

Charles Lindbergh was a hero. He was promoted to Colonel, awarded the Distinguished Flying Cross, the Congressional Medal, the French Cross of the Legion d'Honneur and the British R.A.F. Cross. The scenes of jubilation in New York were incredible. In the noisiest parade ever held in the city, 1800 tons of paper were used to make a 'mail storm', twelve times as much as used in previous Armistice Day celebrations. He received 55 000 telegrams, one signed with 17 500 names and carried in a scroll 520 feet long by ten messenger boys. A Sunday newspaper devoted 100 columns to him as he made an air tour of seventy eight cities and every state in the union.

In his simple way Lindbergh lived through one of the most exhausting publicities ever turned on a single individual. He was commercialised - seriously telling the world that his Wright engine, his AC sparkplugs and Waterman pen all functioned superbly - and became a diplomatic export. Personally invited by President Callas, he made a record breaking non-stop flight from Washington to Mexico City in December, 1927, to be greeted at Valbuena Field by 150 000 Mexicans. For his goodwill mission (totalling 7860 miles) through sixteen South American countries he was awarded the Woodrow Wilson medal and \$25 000. By steering a middle course through sentimentality and commercialism, he brought a new power and vitality to diplomacy. It was no coincidence that in 1931 the Stimson administration specifically altered a previously hostile attitude towards Mexico and other South American countries.

While in Mexico Lindbergh met Anne Morrow, daughter of the US Ambassador, and in May, 1929, they were married in New Jersey. In March, 1932, Lindbergh's son was kidnapped from their home, and the whole apparatus of the press and radio was horrifyingly used to impede the apprehension of the criminals. An army of reporters and photographers invaded the home, obliterating all foot-prints and clues. Such was the publicity that when the baby was found buried four years later a business man bought the piece of ground on which he lay. Lindbergh immediately left the USA for Britain and Europe, returning in 1939.

Despite his support for the policy of non-intervention (inherited from his father who opposed American entry into W.W.I,) after Pearl Harbour he served as a consultant to the Ford Motor Co. and United Aircraft Co., flying fighters in the Pacific Zone. After investigating notorious German aviation developments in 1945, he joined the National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics. For his war efforts he received the Congressional Medal of Honour, the Guggenheim Medal and Wright Brothers Memorial Trophy. In 1953 his autobiography, "Spirit of St. Louis," was awarded the Pulitzer Prize for a biography, and Warner Brothers paid a large sum for the film rights. On 26th August, 1974, Lindbergh died of cancer on the island of Maui, in the Hawaiian group, survived by his wife and a son.

Why did Lindbergh achieve such fame? The airplane was no longer a novelty, the Atlantic had been crossed before by Alcock and Brown, the world had already been circumnavigated and the North Pole reached. Even as he journeyed back to the USA in the 'Memphis' so another American, Charles Levine, had crossed the Atlantic with a passenger, Clarence Chamberlain. The answer is that Lindbergh's flight revolutionised the capabilities of aviation. An epoch closed and a new, exciting one began. The consequences of his fame involved him in tragic personal grief, engaged him in a bitter class controversy, made him a fugitive from the American public; it initiated high power diplomacy and allowed him to play a leading role in the growth of aviation commercialism. as well as in space technology. Charles Lindbergh, a hero in the old sense of the word, but a vague memory in today's advanced stage of exploration.

NB. Lindbergh's trans-Atlantic flight took 33 hours in a plane with a top speed of 129 m.p.h. On the 9th Sept. 1974 an American SR71 Blackbird spy plane flew the same distance in less than two hours; this plane has a top speed of nearly 2000 m.p.h. It then flew the 5400 miles from London to Los Angeles in 3hr 47 mins., beating the sun!

Nursery Rhymes.

Humpty Dumpty.

Either Richard III of England (supposedly a hunchback) who fell during a battle in 1485, at Bosworth, or to Thomas Cromwell, Chancellor to Henry VIII, who was beheaded. In neither instance could "all the king's horses and all the king's men" put him together again. Portraits of the two men show the epithet to be more appropriate to the short, bulky, Cromwell.

Mary, Mary, Quite Contrary.

Mary Tudor, who turned England back to Catholicism, 'contrary' to her brother Edward VI, and father Henry VIII. Cockle shells were worn in the hats of pilgrims on their way to the shrines of saints to indicate the pious nature of their journeys, the silver bells were those again allowed to be rung at the altar during the elevation of the Host, and the 'pretty maids all in a row' were nuns in the re-opened convents!

The Three Blind Mice were possibly bishops who rebelled against Mary and who were thus decapitated 'with a carving knife.'

CHINA'S ROLE IN AFRICA.

M.Morkel. 16.

Although Chinese explorers and traders established contacts along Africa's east and north coasts as far back as the second century AD, these links were broken in the 14th with the rise of European mercantile power, and China remained virtually cut off from Africa for almost 500 years. It was not until the Afro-Asian Conference held in 1955 that modern China showed a renewed interest in Africa and the Middle East. Then in a single decade Peking's aggressive foreign policy succeeded in making a considerable impact on modern Africa. The vigour of self-aggrandizement of Chinese policies and propaganda have led to extravagant claims being made about their influence in Africa. There has even been talk of China trying to make a "grab" for the continent to provide its 735 million people with "lebensraum". But the policies of the Peoples' Republic of China are more sophisticated and more complex than this superficial view suggests.

EARLY CHINESE PENETRATION

China re-entered Africa through the Middle East under the banner of the Chinese Islamic Association. Egypt in 1956 was the first African government to recognize Peking - Morocco and Sudan followed in 1958. By then, however, China's role in Africa was beginning to change. Although there was still little evidence of the coming Sino-Soviet rupture, the divergence of interests and policies of the two communist world centres was being subtly manifested.

One early manifestation was the rivalry between Soviet and Chinese diplomats in persuading important African politicians, students and journalists to visit their countries in order to encourage better relations. At a time when the Soviets under Khrushchev were moving toward "peaceful co-existence" and toward a detente with the United States, China's diplomats in Africa were vigorously denouncing the former course as a betrayal of the cause of "national liberation movements" and the latter as a betrayal of true Marxist-Leninist ideology. In place of a world dominated by the Americans and the Soviets, China proposed an International United Front comprising 90% of the world's population in Africa, Asia and Latin America.

The Sino-Soviet rivalry in Africa has been conducted mainly within and through the Afro-Asian Peoples Solidarity Council which was established in Cairo in 1958 and which is used by both Peking and Moscow especially in furthering their non-official relations with African countries. Presenting themselves as "non-whites" or "coloureds", the Chinese promoted the view that the "poor nations of the world, mainly non-white, should unite against the richer, industrialized nations which are mainly white - including the Russians" Later the Chinese played down this racist line, when they found how it was disliked by the Africans and when it hindered their efforts to win support from the communist parties of Europe and Latin America. Another characteristic of Chinese policy of this early period was to choose a couple of prominent African politicians to be the favoured recipients of financial aid. These selected favourites were to use the money to pursue their own political objectives and at the same time they were expected to make themselves useful to the Chinese by promoting their contacts with African governments, ruling parties and trade unions. However, all did not prove reliable but many found it useful to co-operate with the Chinese in spreading suspicion and hatred, especially of American policies, without necessarily going against their own governments. In this way the Chinese established a nucleus of propagandists with a will to react at a signal from Peking.

CHINESE INFLUENCE IN DECLINE

Chou En-lai's journey to Africa in late 1963 and early 1964 marked the high tide of Chinese influence on the continent. From that time the tide ebbed

except for a while in late 1964 during the Congo rebellion. The visit of the Chinese premier was undoubtedly a propaganda success, greatly helped by two events. The first was President de Gaulle's decision to recognize Peking and his encouragement to former French states to do the same and the second was the successful revolution in Zanzibar in January 1964. Many feared that China had a hand in the revolution in an attempt to establish a bridgehead to the continent. This however proved not the case and in the end China derived less political advantage from it than the Soviets who, working through the East Germans, successfully outmanoeuvred them.

China attached much importance to the second Afro-Asian Conference, held in Algiers in 1965 because it would have given them an opportunity to stake a claim for the leadership of the Afro-Asian world at a time when the war in Vietnam had placed the Americans and the Soviets at a serious disadvantage.

How successful, in fact, has China's role been in Africa? How real is its influence and where does it lie? By 1965 16 of Africa's 37 independent states recognized Peking. Kenya, a state which first welcomed communism at its independence in 1963, later cut relations with China largely because of Kenya's resentment over Chinese interference in its internal affairs. The kingdom of Burundi who offered a base for Chinese efforts to assist the Congo also broke off relations with China after the assassination of its prime minister in 1965. Malawi, too, strongly denounced Chinese intervention in its affairs, while its neighbour Zambia adopted a more cautious but suspicious attitude. The emperor of Ethiopia failed to extend diplomatic recognition to Peking, though he had welcomed Chou En-lai to his capital. Even in the United Arab Republic, China's best friend on the continent, there was evidence of uneasiness about Chinese policies. Ghana's relation with Peking was friendly rather than close. Nkrumah criticised China's decision to enter the nuclear arms race and her attempts to undermine the United Nations. Of all the African states, the two that looked with greatest favour on China were two of the poorest - Mali and Zaire.

In Tanzania, China's position was unique. Nyerere forbade any Chinese interference on the mainland especially in internal matters. In Zanzibar however, where a revolutionary atmosphere still persisted, Communist diplomats were bound to intervene. China's interests in trying to establish a strong position in Tanzania are obvious. Dar-es-Salaam is the headquarters of the National Liberation Committee maintained by the Organisation of African Unity to help the armed struggle against colonialism in central and southern Africa. It is also the headquarters of many of the liberation movements and it offers opportunities for maintaining contacts over a wide area of tropical Africa. The large Chinese mission in Dar-es-Salaam makes the most of the opportunities offered by Tanzania's non-alignment policies to pursue diplomatic policies openly and paradiplomatic activities surreptitiously.

It is not difficult to see why the revolutionary fervour of China's politics should make it hard for Peking to maintain normal relations with any but the more radical African governments. On the other hand, one might have supposed that its attitudes and uncompromising commitment to armed struggle would make it a natural ally of the African liberation movements. Surprisingly this is not the case.

As of now, none of the major liberation movements has developed an alliance primarily with Peking, nor do any of them reflect Peking's Communist ideology to any significant extent. Chinese efforts have been directed towards securing a special relationship with the African National Congress (ANC) of South Africa, the Liberation Front of Mocambique and the Union of the Peoples of Angola. The Soviets also wish to engage the active co-operation of the major liberation movements in Southern Africa and the

Portuguese territories, but they are not anxious to support rebel groups in the already independent African states.

Africa in China's World View.

What conclusions can be drawn from this brief survey? First, China is a power to be reckoned with in Africa, especially when it comes to situations involving rebellion and violence. Second, the Chinese are as capable of making mistakes as anyone else. Third, the Chinese tactics of trying to maintain normal diplomatic relations with African states while at the same time trying to promote real Marxist/Leninist revolutions in the continent has involved them not only in complex diplomatic manoeuvres but in actual conflicts with many of the established governments.

China's aid to Africa is relatively small compared with Western and Soviet aid but nevertheless China is devoting a larger part of its resources to Africa than it does to Asia. Why does it do this? Discounting the accusation that China wishes to 'expand into Africa' the reasons must be found in its ideological commitment and in its national interests. These are, of course, never separable, however much they may be disguised. In fact Chou En-lai admits that his country's policy of assisting other countries is of 'mutual benefit' because any weakening of imperialism benefits China; similarly the weakening of "revisionism" (meaning the Soviets) also benefits China.

Peking's policies and tactics in Africa are naturally determined by the country's own recent revolutionary experience. The whole world has become simply a vast projection of China's own stage on which to enact the theories of Mao Tse-tung. The lessons he learnt on the Long March have been crystallised into five principals which guide China's African policies; these have been officially stated and can be paraphrased as follows:

- i. Socialism can be achieved only through the proletariat waging an armed struggle;
- ii. the peasants are the indispensable allies of the proletariat in this struggle which involves the 'countryside' besieging the 'towns.'
- iii. US imperialism is the arch-enemy of peoples' revolutions everywhere;
- iv. since the 'revolution of the oppressed nations is the indispensable ally of the proletarian revolution,' it is necessary for the workers of all countries to unite;
- v. successful Marxist/Leninist revolutions within any country depend on its having a "revolutionary proletarian party."

These ideological concepts can be simply and rationally restated in the terms of China's own national interests which it seeks to promote through its foreign policies. Its major concern is to avoid total isolation. China's back door was secure only as long as Sino-Soviet friendship could be preserved. When Khrushchev began to seek a detente with the US, Chinese fears of total isolation were greatly intensified, and it was Khrushchev's search for this agreement with President Kennedy that finally led to the break between the two Communist capitals.

To prevent being 'besieged' - a crucial idea in Chinese thinking - by the USSR and US, Peking embarked on its aggressive policies to win the allegiance of the 'third world' against the two super-powers. Seen in this perspective, Chinese foreign policy in Africa makes sense, but its methods in pursuing these objectives are complicated by its revolutionary experience, which dictates its diplomatic tactics. By simultaneously pursuing the long-term objective of "the inevitability and necessity of an armed struggle to achieve a true socialist society" with the short term objective of establishing normal diplomatic relations with as many governments as

possible, the Chinese have created an appalling dilemma for themselves and for others in Africa.

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NB. According to a report in the Rhodesia Herald in April, 1974, the Chinese invested \$558m in Africa last year, which is 100 times more than the Russian total. Twenty three countries accept Chinese aid.

THE MILITARY COUP IN PORTUGAL.

P.Ouborg. 4A.

Causes.

Undoubtedly the man who inspired the coup was Antonio di Spínola, whether he intended to do so or not. Although there has been military discontent in Portugal ever since the war in Africa began thirteen years ago, the whole situation needed a detonator which came in the form of Spínola's controversial book, "Portugal and the Future." The book deals with the solution to Portugal's three wars in Africa, namely those in Guinea Bissau, Angola and Mocambique. Spínola was well qualified to write the book being a veteran of the war in Africa.

Antonio is the son of a wealthy businessman who had close ties with Antonio Salazaar, the man who ruled Portugal for nearly forty years before his death in 1970. Spínola's military career began at the age of twenty and he fought on the side of France in the Spanish Civil War. In 1942 he was with Nazi forces besieging Stalingrad but did not fight for them. After the war he served in the Azores and commanded the key Lisbon unit of the National Republican Guard.

Spínola displayed an immediate interest in Africa almost as soon as fighting broke out there by volunteering to serve in Angola. His real experiences with terrorism came with five years service in Guinea Bissau, the smallest of Lisbon's three trouble spots. In this relatively short period he became a hero among white and black soldiers alike and developed his realistic ideas on terrorism as he came into close contact with it. Allegedly he even had talks with the leader of the terrorists, Amílcar Cabral (a Portuguese incidentally) and stated that the problem could be solved by such contact. This line of reasoning was to form the basis of his book.

In 1972 he was Governor and Commander-in-Chief of the territory and when he returned to Portugal in 1973 he received a hero's welcome. He became Portugal's most decorated soldier when he was awarded the Order of the Tower and the Sword. The monocled General was promoted to a specially created post of Deputy Chief of Staff of the Armed Forces, which was introduced by a grateful government. Far from being satisfied with his life Spínola became more and more agitated as he brooded over the situation in Africa.

The appearance of another book on Africa, "The Portuguese Answer" by Kaulza d'Ariaga, (formerly Head of the Armed Forces in Mocambique) made up Spínola's mind for him. The book glorified the performance of the Portuguese soldier in Africa, an idea which conflicted totally with Spínola's opinion. His reply was to write his own book in which he states that to the wars in Africa "... there is no viable military solution." He outlined a political solution under which the terrorists would join in a federation giving them almost equal status with the mother country. He also advocated more freedom for the blacks in the colonies. Spínola emphasised that his book was not intended to start a revolution but was merely an invitation to discussion to the people of Portugal and her provinces. The book became an immediate best-seller and went through two printings. However it also brought on his head

the wrath of President Americo Tomas and other hard liners left over from the days of the authoritarian Prime Minister, Antonio Salazaar.

Immediately following this came a series of events which were to leave the ruling man Marcello Caetano (who succeeded Salazaar in 1968) with a potential crisis on his hands.

The initial reaction was an attempt by Caetano to convince the people of Portugal (and himself) of the soundness of the military situation in Africa and the loyalty of the armed forces to his regime. The single-party parliament unanimously passed a resolution supporting the government's policy in Africa. At a ceremony in the National Assembly in Lisbon over one hundred generals pledged their support and that of their services. Absent from the ceremony were Generals Spinoia and Gomes (Costa Gomes was Chief of Staff of the Army and had cleared Spinoia's book for publication.) On 14th March Spinoia was dismissed from his post and replaced by General Iuz Cunha who had been a hard line defence minister under Salazaar.

Two days later 200 officers and enlisted men attempted a military coup but failed miserably. They started fifty miles north of Lisbon and marched on the capital but when confronted by loyal troops they turned back and were disarmed without a shot being fired.

Also following the appearance of the book came the arrest of one of Spinoia's closest friends, Lt.Col Joao Almieda Bruno, who had served with him in Guinea Bissau for three years. Other officers are reported to have been arrested or sent to posts in the Azores or Madeira, far from the troubles of Lisbon. No move was made to detain either Spinoia or Gomes.

Thus the stage was set for some kind of drama. The ingredients of the explosive situation had been a man and his book, the repressive measures taken by an authoritarian government, a thirteen year old war which was draining the country of money and man-power (over 40% of the national budget went to defence) and a country from which over a million people had fled to seek better economic opportunities and to escape the hated military draft.

Events.

On Thursday, April 25th, a second military coup took place: this one was successful. The coup was swift, well organised and almost bloodless. "TO THE POINT" magazine sums up the whole affair neatly - "Marcello Caetano's regime was quickly bulldozed off the site by military forces under the command of eager young officers. Within nine hours the government surrendered and a day later the coup was complete". Preparations for the coup began early in the Portuguese spring with secret meetings of military officers on "family picnics". It was agreed that the signal for the coup would be broadcast on the radio. At 10.55 on the night preceeding the chosen day the announcer would give the time and immediately play a recording of a song called "After we Say Good-bye" (Depois do Adios), and two hours later he would play a folk song containing the words "dark city". Since Spinoia's Lisbon home was under regular police scrutiny, it seems he wasn't very active in these preparations.

Late on Wednesday night (the 24th) the first song was broadcast, and early the following morning, the second. In the hours before dawn heavily armed infantry units, in Jeeps and artillery, were positioned around strategic positions in Lisbon and Oporto (a sea-side town in northern Portugal).

Lisbon awoke on the 25th to find that tanks had surrounded the Defence Ministry, the presidential palace, the National Bank and Lisbon's international airport. Most of the bloodshed and action occurred around the headquarters of the detested secret police (the D.G.S. which stands for Direcao Geral de Seguranca or Directorate General of Security). Officers of the D.G.S. who

feared for their lives (and rightly so) barricaded themselves inside. Some of them tried to break away through the cordon surrounding them by racing through it in a truck and firing wildly into the crowd - 5 civilians were killed and 40 others injured. One D.G.S. man was killed in the clash and the rest managed to escape back into the buildings where some time later they surrendered to the infuriated crowd without further skirmishing. With the collapse of the D.G.S. strong-hold the last opposition to the coup went also.

Within nine hours Caetano's regime had given way and soon afterwards President Americo Tomas was captured at the headquarters of a loyal regiment of lancers where he had been taking refuge. Both men, together with five key ministers of the routed government, agreed to being exiled to the Portuguese island of Madeira. Spinoia went with the two former leaders to the plane "in a moving display of passion and embraced Caetano at the door" (TIME magazine).

The formation of a military junta consisting of seven men followed. They were:-

General Antonio de Spinoia at its head.

General Costa Gomes, re-appointed as Head of the General Staff of the Armed Forces.

General Jaime Silverio Marques became Commander in Chief of the Army. He had also served in Angola.

Colonel Galvao de Melo. An ace jet pilot who commanded the 9th air base in Luanda.

Rear-Admiral Pinheiro de Azevedo became Commander in Chief of the navy.

Served in the northern Angolan campaigns.

Commander Alva Rosa Coutinho. Fought with distinction in Angola.

General Diego Neto. Appointed Commander in Chief of the Air Force.

These seven men became the head of the new Portugal, and all had distinguished service records in the African territories.

Thus in the after-math of a coup almost free of violence, after the initial excitement of a political upheaval, a new Portugal slowly comes down to earth once more. The big question is, "Has the coup brought a solution to the African wars?" As Spinoia wrote in his book, "The future of Portugal depends on an adequate solution to the war in which we are involved.... it is not national unity that is at stake, but imperial unity and today's conscience does not accept empires."

Events Immediately After the Coup.

The first moves of the new Junta were probably aimed at gaining popularity. Many repressive measures of the old regime were abolished. At a press conference Spinoia announced the first democratic institution - popular elections with political freedom and the dissolution of the National Popular Action Group (the only legal party before the coup). The most reactive elements to this were the socialists and the communists. They were feeding on a new found freedom of speech and action and the hero's return accorded to the exiled socialist leader, Mario Soares. The chants of "Liberty, liberty" which had filled the streets immediately after the coup were replaced with calls of, "Socialism, socialism" and "Get out of Africa". All over Lisbon the hammer and the sickle was daubed on the walls.

There are few parties besides the socialists likely to contest the elections:-

The Liberals, a left wing organisation backed by the student movement.

The Monarchists, consisting of those who realise that the monarchy cannot be restored.

The movement of ex-servicemen and ex-colonialists.

This last group might form a coalition with Monarchists. The communists might also be allowed to form a party. Spinola promised that these elections would be held within a year.

The next liberal measure to be introduced was the lifting of censorship of the press. As a result most papers featured huge stories on the freeing of political prisoners which was the Junta's most popular move. The immediate release of some 170 political detainees had been ordered by the Junta. For many years there had been rumours that the terrible D.G.S. tortured these political prisoners and on that day they were verified with the discovery of the torture rooms and the reports of workers in the prison. On April 28th the Church wisely threw its weight behind the coup.

In every country there are critics of the government but seldom do they get the chance to test their theories. Now Spinola found himself at the head of the country. Soon Portugal was to see his efforts crumble on the question of the colonies.

Yet internally things were being accomplished. At the same press conference he promised the replacement of the Junta within three weeks by a largely civilian provisional government. This was confirmed on May 15th when a Junta spokesman announced that Spinola would take over as the new President of Portugal. He added that a provisional government had been formed, according to promise, and that Spinola would disclose their names the following day.

Results - the Colonies in Africa.

A detailed discussion on the colonies is out of the scope of this essay since it would take too long. However, I will outline the effects on the colonies up to now. It may be said that Spinola has so far solved nothing - unless chaos, division and handing over to terrorism can be called progress towards Spinola's ideal of a multi-racial, peaceful, economically stable and prosperous federation of self governing states. In Mozambique he has failed dismally. His plans for talks with FRELIMO disintegrated as the latter made it clear that they would settle for nothing less than independence for the territory with themselves in control. The result is total economic and political chaos and an exodus of whites. FRELIMO is on the verge of a take over. Guinea Bissau has been taken over by terrorists under Luis Cabral. After talks with the terrorist leaders in Algiers and London, the Portuguese announced that they were willing to give independence to the province. On August 26th an agreement was signed granting independence to Guinea Bissau taking effect on September 10th.

Of the three provinces Angola is standing firm. But there is internal division against the Portuguese Government. TO THE POINT says, "It is not an exodus but a successful defiance". The 600,000 whites and the 200,000 mulattos have formed an alliance against the representative of the Junta, Admiral Rosa Coutinho, who is said to be a communist sympathiser. Their cry was "Anglo sim, Comunismo NAO" (Angola; yes, communism NO) and they expressed their wish to form a multi-racial Angola.

Events are moving so swiftly that things might have changed by the time this article is published.

To sum up the coup - a man and his book and a revolution, the results of which in the long run will affect the future of southern Africa and the western world in the face of Communism.

References : Time Magazine; To The Point Magazine; The Umtali Post; The Rhodesia Herald; The Sunday Mail; The Bulawayo Chronicle; The S.A. Sunday Times; The Christian Science Monitor; Radio Rhodesia; Radio South Africa.

THE SIX-DAY WAR.

D.Wylie. 3A1.

What follows is a precis of a personal project being done by the writer.

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The Six-Day War in the Middle East has been hailed as the most outstanding military campaign of the century - a campaign which brought an Arab-surrounded Israel an overwhelming victory and a powerful new status in the Arab world.

Although the war itself lasted only six days (June 5-10th, 1967) the reasons for its ever happening can be traced back over three times as many years - to Israel's declaration of independence on 14th May, 1948. She had to fight for her life to keep that independence, and her victory only served to heighten an intense Arab hatred. The Suez Crisis of 1956 brought another Israeli victory; 1967 saw the most crushing Arab defeat of them all, but that hatred for tiny Israel still blazes.

In January 1965 the El Fatah terrorist organisation was formed, and for over two years infiltrators harassed Israel's borders. At last, on May 12th, 1967, a direct threat was issued: Israel would "find the time, the place and the means to combat the aggressor." At the same time Russia warned (erroneously) of a massive Israeli military build-up on Syria's border; the result was an immediate mobilisation of Egyptian, Jordanian and Syrian forces. On May 17th Egypt requested the withdrawal of the United Nations Emergency Force, a peace-keeping contingent stationed on the Egyptian-Israeli frontier since 1956. The United Nations complied. When UNEF withdrew on May 19th, they relinquished the fortress of Sharm el Sheikh, the guns of which command the Straits of Tiran at the mouth of the Gulf of Aquaba, at the head of which lies the Israeli port of Eilat. President Nasser of Egypt promptly closed the Straits to Israeli shipping, a move which Israel called an 'act of aggression' and which was condemned by both the USA and Britain. These two powers decided to propose a maritime declaration to ensure free shipping in the Gulf. When the declaration failed to materialise, Israel decided to act alone. On June 4th she decided on war.

Israel struck first - with devastating effect - just after 7.30 am on June 5th. Within 170 minutes the Israeli Air Force had virtually wiped out Egyptian air power, thus leaving her ground forces free of air attack. These forces advanced in a pincer movement which outflanked the central Egyptian Sinai headquarters at Bir Gifgafa on June 7th, El Arish and the Gaza Strip in the north having already fallen. Sharm el Sheik in the far south fell without a shot. On the eastern front the Jordanians fought tenaciously but without air cover they were driven back until, on June 7th, Jerusalem came under complete Israeli control for the first time in 2 000 years. By June 9th Israeli forces had occupied all Jordan west of the River Jordan. Meanwhile the entire Sinai Peninsula had been overrun as far as the Suez Canal, seven Egyptian divisions having been destroyed or rendered useless. On June 8th Israel and Egypt signed a cease-fire, but fighting continued on the Syrian front where Israeli forces had advanced to within forty miles of Damascus. Syrian resistance collapsed and a cease-fire came into effect on June 10th. Jordan withdrew with her allies' defeat.

And defeat it was. Israel had occupied an area almost four times her original size, had routed three armies each larger than her own and had attained a measure of air superiority over her Arab neighbours that has never been equalled in the history of aerial warfare. Massive victory though it was however, it solved no problem in the Middle East; the Arab world never accept co-existence with the Jew - and probably never will - and there has been almost continuous fighting ever since.

HISTORY SOCIETY CROSSWORD.

Write your answers to this crossword on a piece of paper and hand them to Mr Barnes before 1st December, 1974. The Society offers a worthwhile prize for the first correct entry opened on that date.

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ACROSS.

1. A stormy day, this 14th July.(8)
4. A telegram that launched a war.(3)
8. A cockney titfer?(2)
9. Occupied by France and Germany in 1923.(4)
10. One clan disrupted an 18th Controller-General of France.(7)
11. A combination in diapers gained independence in 1947.(5)
12. The fields on which Waterloo was won?(4)
13. Me? In whose struggle?(4)
15. Africa's Aardvark as Hitler's coal deposits.(4)
16. 18th Austrian headquarters in Italy.(5)
17. A nag in a Latin capital as part of Italian Unification?(7)
19. This chronological basic factor is delicious as a fruit!(4)
20. A Protean leaves Bonaparte degreed.(2)
21. The Chinese Republic's first doctor?(3)
22. Vanes near the Austrian border marked the end of the road for Louis XVI.(8)

DOWN.

1. A carriage as a divided city?(6)
2. Riot and retrieval denote the material gains of a settlement.(11)
3. 3 miles distant to perpetuate peace in 1919.(6)
5. He is the head of Manicaland?(3)
6. Baron Heinrich Friedrich Karl vom und zen _____, Prussian social reformer.(5)
7. Napoleon's defeat of the Austrians, 1800.(11)
13. A colourful battle in Italy, 1859.(7)
14. Two points join with glee for this political thinker.(6)
15. Together with the Croats and Slavs they formed Yugoslavia.(5)
18. A movement for unity centred on Addis Ababa.(3)